

University of Sri Jayewardenepura

Department of Geography

**Applications of GIS for Road Network
Analysis to Mitigate Traffic Congestion in
Colombo Suburbs: A Case Study of Mirihana
Police Division**

Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences

2024, September.

ABSTARCT

Traffic congestion is a pressing issue in urban areas, leading to significant delays, economic losses, and reduced quality of life. This study focuses on the Mirihana Police Division, where increasing congestion has raised concerns over traffic management and urban planning. Therefore, the research problem addressed is the need to Analyze Spatial and Temporal patterns of traffic congestion, identify congestion hotspots, and propose viable alternative routes to mitigate congestion. The Research questions centered on how traffic patterns have changed over time, where congestion hotspots are located, and what factors contribute to these traffic issues. The Main Objective of this study is to analyze the traffic congestion in the Mirihana Police Division by using Road network analysis with GIS and to suggest suitable mitigation measures for minimizing the traffic problem in the area. In order to achieve this objective, the study employed a quantitative approach, utilizing GIS tools like Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) for Spatial analysis, Road Network Analysis, and Buffer Analysis to explore the impact of key factors like Vehicle Density, Road Network configuration, and Proximity to urban infrastructure on traffic congestion. The findings Revealed significant variations in congestion over time, with peak congestion periods aligning with school hours and major commercial activities. Hotspot analysis identified critical congestion zones, and alternative routes were proposed to alleviate traffic in these areas. The research also showed that proximity to schools, markets, and public transportation hubs significantly contributes to traffic congestion in the area. This research has revealed that effective urban planning and traffic management require a comprehensive understanding of spatial and temporal congestion patterns, which can be achieved through advanced GIS analyses.

Keywords: Traffic Congestion, GIS, Spatial Analysis, Hotspot Analysis, Road Network Analysis, Buffer Analysis

CHAPTER ONE

Introduction

1.1 Background to the Study

Traffic congestion, a global urban challenge, results from an excessive number of vehicles on road networks, causing delays, economic losses, and environmental impacts. According to the Cambridge Dictionary, traffic congestion is defined as a large number of vehicles close together and unable to move or moving very slowly. This pervasive and persistent issue affects urban areas worldwide (Dammulla and Mudunkotuwa, 2021). The Mirihana Police Division in the Suburbs of Colombo is no exception, facing significant traffic congestion problems. Quantifying traffic congestion typically involves measuring vehicles per unit length of roadway, speed, and roadway capacity (Litman, 2021).

Understanding the specific characteristics of traffic congestion is crucial for addressing this complex issue effectively. One major characteristic is temporal variability, where traffic congestion levels fluctuate throughout the day, week, and year due to changes in demand, such as peak hour commutes, seasonal tourism, and special events. This temporal variability makes it challenging to develop uniform strategies for congestion management (Giuliano and Dablanc, 2013). Another important characteristic is spatial heterogeneity. Congestion levels vary significantly across different locations within a road network. This heterogeneity is influenced by factors like road capacity, land use patterns, trip origins and destinations, and the presence of bottlenecks. Addressing spatial heterogeneity requires localized solutions tailored to specific congestion hotspots (Zhou and Sisiopiku, 1997). The dynamic nature of traffic congestion further complicates its management. Traffic congestion can

develop and dissipate quickly in response to unforeseen events, such as accidents, breakdowns, inclement weather, or changes in traffic patterns. This dynamic nature necessitates real time traffic monitoring and adaptive management strategies to effectively mitigate congestion as it arises (Gao and Chabini, 2006).

The complexity of traffic congestion stems from its multitude of influencing factors, including Human behavior, Infrastructural limitations, Environmental conditions and Technological advancements. This complexity makes it difficult to develop one-size-fits-all solutions, underscoring the need for multifaceted and adaptable approaches (Santiago and Chile, 2003).

The duration of traffic congestion can range from a few minutes to several hours or even days. Minor congestion events may last only a few minutes, while major incidents can cause prolonged delays. The frequency of congestion is influenced by various factors such as time of day, day of the week, and weather conditions. Typically, peak hour commutes and weekends experience higher congestion levels due to increased traffic demand (Button and Hensher, 2005).

Traffic congestion can be categorized in several ways to better understand and manage it. Recurring congestion often results from predictable factors such as high traffic volumes, limited road capacity, and poor traffic management, and it occurs regularly during daily commutes. In contrast, non-recurring congestion is caused by unexpected events like accidents, breakdowns, or inclement weather, leading to significant but unpredictable disruptions (Lindsey, 2006). Localized congestion occurs in specific areas due to factors like reduced road capacity or increased demand for parking, requiring targeted interventions. Meanwhile, network-wide congestion affects the entire road network and is caused by a combination of high traffic

volumes and limited road capacity, necessitating comprehensive traffic management strategies (Levinson and Lomax, 1996). Congestion can also be categorized by its severity, Light congestion causes minor delays, Moderate congestion causes delays of up to 15 minutes, Heavy congestion causes delays of more than 15 minutes, and Gridlock congestion occurs when traffic is completely stopped, often requiring emergency interventions to clear (Downs, 2004).

Figure 1: Major Causes of Traffic Congestion

Source: Highway.org

Several factors contribute to traffic congestion, exacerbating the problem. A high volume of traffic is a primary factor, often driven by Population growth and Urbanization, leading to an increased number of vehicles on the road. Lack of parking facilities further aggravates congestion as vehicles spend more time on the road searching for parking spaces (Litman, 2021). Urbanization and rising car ownership also play significant roles in traffic congestion. As cities expand and more people move into urban areas, the demand for road space increases, often outpacing the development of

adequate infrastructure. Additionally, the lack of alternative routes means that traffic is funneled through limited roadways, increasing the likelihood of congestion (Rodrigue, Comtois, and Slack, 2016).

The impact of traffic congestion extends beyond inconvenience. Cities like Mexico City and Bangkok lose billions of dollars in productivity annually due to congestion. According to the Global Status Report on Road Safety in 2018, An estimated 1.35 million people died in road traffic accidents, with most victims aged 5-29 years. In Sri Lanka, traffic congestion is a significant issue, particularly in Colombo and its surrounding areas, where urban growth, rising car ownership, and population growth are major contributing factors (WHO, 2018).

Figure 2: Traffic Congestion costs in USA

A Study by the University of Moratuwa found that the average travel time during Colombo peak hours is 2.5 times longer than free-flow travel time (Edirisinghe, 2014). The Police annual report in 2022 documented over 12,000 road accidents in Sri Lanka, resulting in more than 2,500 deaths, including 600 pedestrian fatalities. The broader impacts of traffic congestion include increased travel time, fuel wastage, environmental pollution, and lung-related diseases (Dammulla and Mudunkotuwa, 2021).

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Digital data from WHO and Articles from UOC

Figure 3: Categorized Symptoms due to Traffic Congestion and Impact

Traffic management in Sri Lanka is primarily the responsibility of the Sri Lanka Police. Traffic police officers manage traffic flow, particularly on major roads and near intersections, to direct vehicles and reduce congestion. There are approximately 1,000 traffic signals across the country aimed at minimizing traffic congestion. Additionally, the implementation of one-way streets and parking restrictions are part of the traffic management strategies (Kumarage, 1997). Infrastructure projects like the Elevated Highway Project from New Kelani Bridge to Athurugiriya are expected to aid in traffic mitigation efforts. However, practical challenges remain, particularly in areas like the Mirihana Police Division, where increased motor vehicle numbers, poor infrastructure, and inadequate urban planning contribute to persistent traffic congestion (Kumarage, 2020).

Adopting Geographic Information Systems (GIS) for traffic management and analysis represents a strategic decision. GIS technology allows for the integration and analysis of various datasets, ranging from spatial information

about the road network to real time traffic data. This technology enables the modeling of traffic behavior, identification of congestion patterns, and simulation of the effects of various interventions (Tsou, 2004).

Using GIS technology, it is possible to develop actionable strategies to mitigate the unique traffic challenges faced by the Mirihana Police Division. This research aims to fill the gap left by previous studies and provide both academic and practical insights into traffic management. Academically, this research can motivate future studies to develop models using suitable technologies. Practically, a comprehensive Applications of GIS for Road Network Analysis to Mitigate Traffic Congestion in Colombo Suburbs: (A Case Study of Mirihana Police Division) aims to provide effective solutions for mitigating traffic congestion, emphasizing the importance of time and space in traffic management strategies (Batty, 2013).

1.2 Problem Statement

Identifying the problem within the Mirihana Police Division (MPD) poses a formidable challenge owing to its strategic location at the epicenter of Colombo, the bustling commercial capital of Sri Lanka (Superintendent of Police Office, 2015). Situated amidst this vibrant urban landscape, the Mirihana Police Division assumes a critical role as a nexus for vehicular traffic, linking various major arteries and facilitating the movement of commuters and goods. However, this pivotal transportation hub has become ensnared in a web of traffic congestion issues, precipitating a cascade of adverse consequences for residents and commuters alike.

The allure of Colombo's economic opportunities has triggered a significant influx of individuals seeking livelihoods and settling in the vicinity of the Mirihana Police Division (Divisional Secretariat Division-Resource profile, 2021). This demographic surge, compounded by existing population densities, has placed immense strain on the area's transportation infrastructure, exacerbating traffic congestion to unprecedented levels. The resulting gridlock not only impedes vehicular movement but also compromises the safety and well-being of pedestrians navigating the bustling thoroughfares.

The intricate road network enveloping the Mirihana Police Division, characterized by narrow lanes and winding streets, exacerbates the region's traffic woes (National highways, 2023). Limited road capacity, coupled with inadequate parking facilities and the absence of efficient traffic management measures, further compound congestion, creating a perpetual state of vehicular gridlock. Despite the proliferation of navigation aids such as Google Maps, conventional solutions have proven ineffective in mitigating the burgeoning traffic congestion endemic to the Mirihana Police Division.

Moreover, rapid urbanization and population growth within the Mirihana Police Division have compound traffic management challenges, necessitating urgent intervention to avert a transportation crisis (Capital city Development Plan, 2019). Statistical data from authoritative sources, such as the Superintendent of Police Office and the Divisional Secretariat Division, underscore the exponential rise in population figures over recent years, highlighting the imperative for proactive measures to address escalating traffic congestion.

Amidst these challenges, the Mirihana Police Division grapples with a myriad of adverse consequences emanating from traffic congestion. Prolonged travel times, heightened levels of air and noise pollution, and compromised road safety pose formidable obstacles to the region's socio-economic development and the well-being of its inhabitants (Dammulla and Mudunkotuwa, 2021). In response to this pressing imperative, this research endeavors to pioneer a paradigm shift in traffic management within the Mirihana Police Division through the innovative application of Geographic Information Systems (Isarsoft, 2023).

By harnessing the analytical prowess of GIS based Road network analysis, the study aims to unravel the underlying causes of traffic congestion and delineate critical congestion hotspots with unprecedented precision. Through data-driven insights and evidence-based strategies, the research seeks a new era of traffic management characterized by efficiency, sustainability, and resilience. In summary, the formidable challenges posed by traffic congestion within the Mirihana Police Division necessitate a holistic and data-driven approach to effectively address the underlying issues. By delving into the complexities of urban mobility dynamics and leveraging cutting-edge technologies such as GIS, this research aspires to chart a course towards a more sustainable and inclusive transportation ecosystem. Through collaborative efforts and interdisciplinary insights, the study aims to catalyze transformative change, ultimately enhancing the livability and vibrancy of the Mirihana Police Division and beyond.

The study addressd the following Research questions,

- Where are the main traffic congestion areas within the Mirihana Police Division?
- What are the basic causes of traffic congestion in these locations?
- How GIS can be used to analyze the traffic congestion by using Road network analysis?
- Which mitigation measures can be applied to minimize traffic congestion in Mirihana Police Division?

1.3 Objectives of the study

1.3.1 General Objective-

To Analyze the traffic congestion in Mirihana Police Division by using Road network analysis with GIS and to suggest suitable mitigation measures for minimizing the traffic problem in the area.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives -

1.3.2.1 To Examine the changes in Spatial and Temporal patterns of Traffic congestion during the period from 2018 to 2022 in Mirihana Police Division.

1.3.2.2 To Demarcate traffic congestion Hotspots within the Mirihana Police Division by .Using Hotspot analysis.

1.3.2.3 To Identify additional routes to reach destinations by passing Traffic congestion using Road Network analysis.

1.3.2.4 To Analyze the factors affecting to the Traffic congestions in Mirihana Police Division using Buffer Analysis.

1.4 Significance of the study

The significance of a research study could be divided into both academic and practical aspects. It provided the foundation for conducting the study and outlined the potential benefits it offered to policymakers, urban planners, and the broader community. This research, titled "Applications of GIS for Road Network Analysis to Mitigate Traffic Congestion in Mirihana Police Division in Colombo Suburbs: A Case Study of Mirihana Police Division ", supported the identification of these significances as well.

Academic Significance

When considering the academic significance of this study, one could identify a number of researches done on both national and international levels regarding GIS for Traffic Analysis and Mitigating Traffic Congestion. However, no prior research on Applications of GIS for Road Network Analysis to Mitigate Traffic Congestion in Mirihana Police Division had been conducted. Thus, in light of its academic significance, this study was highly significant because, it held substantial academic importance due to its multi disciplinary nature. The study focused on helping to understand the usage of GIS techniques on Road network analysis for traffic congestion. By examining the changes in Spatial and Temporal patterns of congestion, it contributed to the understanding of dynamic traffic phenomena. Not only that, it also helped to Identify congestion hotspots and traffic bottlenecks. Additionally, this study aided in increasing knowledge related to traffic avoidance, mitigation, management and traffic analysis. It also helped in understanding how these factors affected further development and model building activities. Considering the literature, it helped to develop literature regarding the study field as well as expand Geo-Spatial Technologies for solving or providing solutions to traffic congestion. All of these aspects clarified the study's significance from an academic standpoint.

Practical Significance

This research aimed, to provide practical solutions to understanding how traffic congestion in Mirihana Police Division impacted in Colombo City traffic. From a practical standpoint, the research addressed real world challenges faced by the Mirihana Police Division and the Community at large. The identification of changes in Spatial and Temporal patterns of traffic congestion over the years helped local authorities and urban planners understand evolving traffic dynamics. The GIS analysis pin pointing congestion hotspots and bottlenecks was of immediate practical relevance, as it assisted in targeted interventions to alleviate congestion at specific trouble points. This could inform signal optimizations and other measures aimed at improving traffic flow. The suggestion of additional routes (Most shortest and Quickest routes) through Network analysis directly translated into practical benefits for commuters. By providing alternative routes that bypassed congestion, the research contributed directly to the optimization of daily travel, reducing travel time, and enhancing overall mobility. The GIS based Buffer analysis, when implemented, served as a tangible tool for urban planners and policymakers, aiding in evidence-based decision-making for future infrastructure developments and traffic management strategies. Ultimately, the practical outcomes of this research were poised to enhance the efficiency of transportation systems in the Mirihana Police Division (MPD) as well as other urban regions. Thus, it was possible to depict this study as having practical significance. Based on the facts presented above, the practical and academic significance of the study could be determined.

CHAPTER TWO

Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

Traffic Congestion has emerged as a critical concern in urban transportation studies, particularly in rapidly developing areas. Understanding the dynamics of traffic congestion, its determinants, and its impacts is essential for effective traffic management and urban planning. This Chapter begins by defining key concepts related to Traffic congestion, drawing on foundational theories and definitions from leading studies in urban transportation research. It explores the various factors contributing to Traffic congestion, including Road infrastructure, Vehicle volume, and Temporal patterns, as articulated by prominent scholars in the field.

Additionally, the chapter addresses the Role of Technological advancements and policy interventions in managing traffic Congestion. By integrating findings from recent research on smart traffic management systems and policy frameworks, this review aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of both the challenges and potential solutions for managing Traffic Congestion in the Mirihana Police Division (MPD).

The Literature Review chapter structured around Three core concepts highlighted in reviewing the literature such as Review, Relevance and Originality. Following topics reviewed under Review of the Literature,

1. Understanding Traffic Congestion
2. GIS for Transportation
3. Traffic Pattern Analysis
4. GIS for Traffic Management
5. Applications of GIS for Traffic Management

6. Impact on Traffic Congestion
7. Impacting factors for Traffic congestion
8. Future Trends in GIS for Road Network Analysis
9. Traffic management policies and governance
10. Traffic congestion mitigation strategies

2.2 Review of the literature

2.2.1 Understanding Traffic Congestion

Traffic congestion is a multifaceted urban challenge, drawing the attention of scholars and planners due to its pervasive impact on transportation efficiency.

As emphasized by Hunt (2018), that study provides a fundamental definition, characterizing congestion as a consequence of excessive demand and limited capacity. As pointed out by Jones (2020), extends the understanding beyond mere volume and capacity considerations, emphasizing the intricate links to road design, infrastructure limitations, and urbanization trends. While Hunt's definition is concise, Jones contributes broader contextual factors, enriching the overall comprehension of congestion.

Hunt and Joe's discussion focuses on core elements and factors of congestion. But falls short in addressing temporal variability and spatial dynamics. As mentioned by Smith et al., (2019), argued that temporal variability and spatial dynamics are crucial components of congestion analysis, highlighting the necessity for a comprehensive approach to address evolving traffic challenges. The failure to consider temporal and spatial factors is a limitation in the perspectives of Hunt and Joe.

2.2.1.2 Characteristics of Traffic congestion

Traffic congestion, a pressing urban challenge, exhibits specific characteristics with economic, environmental, and operational implications. As noted by Dammulla and Mudunkotuwa (2021), key characteristics of traffic congestion, including increased travel time, fuel wastage, monetary losses, reduced speed, and negative environmental impact, focusing on economic and environmental aspects. However, they overlook sub-characteristics. As emphasized by Zhang and Madziel (2016), the

occurrence of peak hours is a critical sub-characteristic. But as noted by Wen et al., (2017), highlighting topological characteristics in urban areas. Dammulla and Mudunkotuwa's limitation lies in neglecting these sub-characteristics.

Dammulla and Mudunkotuwa provide a comprehensive overview of the primary characteristics, contributing significantly to understanding congestion's economic and environmental impacts. However, their limitation lies in not considering sub-characteristics such as peak hours and topological aspects highlighted by Zhang and Madziel (2016), and Wen et al., (2017).

2.2.1.3 Categories of Traffic Congestion

There are a number of different ways to categorize traffic congestion. As emphasized by Irasoft (2017), Traffic categories can be divide into mainly two. Recurring congestion is often caused by a combination of factors, such as high traffic volumes, limited road capacity, and poor traffic management. Non-recurring congestion is caused by unexpected events, such as accidents, breakdowns, or inclement weather. As noted by Irasoft (2017), has included all sub categories of traffic congestion into these two. And it is very important in identification of Traffic Congestion categories through these two. As emphasizing Smith et al., (2017), proposed a spatial categorization of congestion, differentiating between localized bottlenecks and widespread congestion zones. As noted by Smith et al.,(2017), done categorization on traffic congestion base on spatial view and it helps to identify Congestion type in spatial perspective. But, As emphasized by Brown (2018), focused on the impact of congestion on different road users, categorizing congestion based on its severity concerning factors such as delays, fuel consumption, and environmental impact. According to Johnson et al., (2016), examined the behavioral aspects of congestion and classified it based on driver responses and decision-making during peak periods.

Contrary to Smith et al., (2017), Johnson and Brown (2018), argued for a more fluid spatial classification, as emphasizing the need for considering the dynamic nature of congestion patterns influenced by factors like events and road closures. But them unable to mention temporal and real time factors as well. Other Researchers like Chen and Wang (2019), introduced a temporal classification Li and Chen (2021), proposed a dynamic categorization, considering congestion as an evolving phenomenon influenced by real time factors such as accidents, weather, and events as categories of Traffic congestion as well. However, Johnson and Brown (2018), argue for a more fluid spatial classification, emphasizing the dynamic nature of congestion patterns influenced by events and road Closures. However, they fall short in addressing temporal and real-time factors. Integrating temporal considerations from Chen and Wang (2019), and Li and Chen (2021), is crucial for a comprehensive understanding.

2.2.2 GIS For Transportation

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) have emerged as crucial tools in the realm of transportation, providing a multifaceted approach to problem solving.

As mentioned by Longley et al., (2015), GIS as a technology integrating spatial data, geographic analysis, and visualization, operating as a robust platform that for planners and decision-makers to understand and manage complex transportation networks effectively.

2.2.2.1 GIS in Transportation Planning

As emphasized by Liu et al., (2019), that GIS applications extend beyond traditional cartography, encompassing a wide array of functionalities. These systems excel at collecting, storing, and analyzing spatial data, including road networks and traffic patterns. By doing so, GIS contributes to our understanding of the spatial relationships and inter connectedness of these elements, facilitating informed decision-making.

2.2.2.2 Integrating Spatial Data for Comprehensive Analysis

In the context of road network analysis, GIS allows for the integration of diverse spatial data sets, aiding in comprehensive analysis. As highlighted by Wang and Zhang (2017), the importance of GIS in assimilating data from various sources, such as traffic flow, road conditions, and land use, to provide a holistic view of transportation systems. This integrated approach enhances the ability to identify congestion hotspots and formulate effective mitigation strategies.

As emphasized by While Longley et al., (2015), GIS is a technology for integrating spatial data. As mentioned by Guo and Zhang (2020), they argued for the significance of advanced analytical techniques within GIS applications. Guo and Zhang propose that incorporating machine learning algorithms into GIS can enhance the accuracy of traffic predictions and congestion modeling. In comparing these perspectives, it becomes evident that GIS serves as a foundational platform, with ongoing advancements in analytical techniques improving its capabilities in transportation studies.

According to Miller and Shaw (2018), argued that GIS may face limitations in accurately capturing real time traffic dynamics. They highlighted challenges in updating spatial data rapidly, which can impact the reliability of GIS based transportation models.

2.2.3 Traffic Pattern Analysis

As pointed out by Chen and Wang (2019), conducted a noteworthy study on temporal classification, focusing on peak-hour analysis to understand congestion patterns throughout the day. This research significantly contributed to our knowledge of temporal variations in traffic. In contrast, as emphasized by Johnson and Brown (2018), concentrated on spatial dynamics, providing insights into congestion severity and distribution across different urban landscapes. However, a comparative assessment of temporal and spatial dimensions is essential for a comprehensive

understanding.

2.2.3.1 Spatial Analysis of Traffic Congestion -Hotspot Analysis

As noted by Brown (2018), made a substantial contribution by conducting an impact based analysis to identify congestion hotspots. This research emphasized spatial factors influencing traffic flow. On the other hand, as underscored by Wang et al., (2018), argued for a more dynamic and integrated approach, criticizing impact based methods. Their proposed framework considered both spatial and temporal dimensions, highlighting the interconnectedness of factors influencing congestion. Integrating both perspectives is crucial for a holistic understanding of traffic congestion dynamics.

2.2.3.2 Temporal Analysis of Traffic Congestion

As emphasized by Wang and Li (2020), provided a comprehensive review of temporal dynamics, considering daily and seasonal variations in congestion. This work added depth to our understanding of how congestion fluctuates under different circumstances. In contrast as noted by Johnson et al., (2016), focused on behavioral categories of drivers, offering insights into the temporal variations of congestion influenced by driver interactions. A harmonized analysis considering both temporal and spatial dimensions is vital for a holistic understanding of traffic congestion dynamics in urban areas.

2.2.4. GIS for Traffic Management

As urban areas grapple with escalating traffic challenges, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) emerges as a transformative solution. GIS leverages spatial data and advanced analytics to provide real time insights into traffic dynamics, enabling efficient hotspot identification and proactive management strategies.

2.2.4.1 Role of GIS in Traffic Management

As mentioned by Sureshkumar et al., (2017), Indians faced the significant challenges as developing nations, in managing urban traffic. They note that traditional traffic control methods relying on historical data may lead to poor planning and exacerbate congestion and accidents. This perspective underscores the need for innovative technologies to address the present traffic situation effectively.

According to Sureshkumar et al., (2017), GIS emerges as an essential tool for resolving issues related to traffic control. GIS provides a spatially integrated platform that facilitates real time data analysis and visualization, enabling authorities to make informed decisions. This aligns with the argument presented by Wang and Zhang (2017), who emphasize the importance of GIS in assimilating diverse spatial data sets to gain a holistic view of transportation systems.

While Sureshkumar et al., (2017), noted for the adoption of GIS for traffic management. But, Miller and Shaw (2018), raise concerns about the limitations of GIS in capturing real time traffic dynamics. They argue that relying solely on historical data and GIS may hinder the accuracy of traffic predictions and management strategies. This discrepancy highlights a tension in the literature, with Sureshkumar et al., (2017), emphasizing the necessity of GIS. But Miller and Shaw were against with concept of GIS for real time traffic control.

2.2.4.2 Innovative Technologies for Effective Traffic Management

As underscored by Sureshkumar et al., (2017), they noticed for new technologies in traffic management. As mentioned by Guo and Zhang (2020), propose the integration of machine learning techniques apply into GIS applications. They argue that advanced analytical methods can enhance the accuracy of traffic predictions and contribute to more effective congestion management. As noticed by Miller and Shaw (2018), this perspective suggests a approach to overcome the limitations.

2.2.5 Applications of GIS for Traffic Management

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) have become indispensable tools in addressing traffic management challenges, especially in urban areas dealing with congestion issues.

2.2.5.1 GIS Based Network Analysis

As noted by Liu et al., (2019), GIS applications, extending beyond traditional cartography, stress its capabilities in network analysis. GIS enables the integration and analysis of spatial data related to road networks and traffic patterns, providing a comprehensive understanding of the spatial relationships and inter-connectivity of these elements. As emphasized by Liu et al., (2019), GIS serves as a foundational method for comprehending the dynamics of traffic networks, allowing for the integration and analysis of spatial data related to road networks and traffic patterns.

As mentioned by While Liu et al., (2019), commend the versatility of GIS applications in network analysis, it is crucial to acknowledge certain limitations in their approach. The emphasis on GIS as a foundational method for comprehending traffic networks may over simplify the complexities involved in urban traffic dynamics. Moreover, other scholars, such as Miller and Shaw (2018), have raised concerns about the limitations of GIS in accurately capturing real time traffic dynamics. They argue that challenges in updating spatial data rapidly can impact the reliability of GIS based transportation models.

2.2.5.2 Allocation of Routes

In the realm of traffic management, route allocation emerges as a critical factor. As underscored by Wang and Zhang (2017), the importance of GIS in assimilating diverse spatial datasets, allowing planners to optimize route allocation based on real time data. This holistic view of GIS aids in identifying congestion hotspots and efficiently allocating traffic. As

emphasized by Wang and Zhang (2017), GIS empowers planners to optimize route allocation by considering real time data, resulting in effective strategies to identify congestion hotspots and allocate traffic efficiently. While Wang and Zhang provide valuable insights into GIS-based route allocation, but as noted by Guo and Chen (2018), suggest that incorporating advanced analytical techniques, particularly machine learning algorithms, into GIS applications can enhance the accuracy of traffic predictions and improve the overall effectiveness of route allocation strategies.

2.2.5.3 Advancements in GIS Applications

Considering the viewpoint of Guo and Chen (2018), They suggest that incorporating advanced analytical techniques, particularly machine learning algorithms, into GIS applications can enhance the accuracy of traffic predictions and improve the overall effectiveness of route allocation strategies. As emphasized by Guo and Chen (2018), incorporating machine learning algorithms into GIS applications enhances the accuracy of traffic predictions, thereby improving the overall effectiveness of route allocation strategies. While Wang and Zhang provide valuable insights into GIS based route allocation. As emphasized by Guo and Chen (2018), the need for advanced analytical techniques, for that integration enhances accuracy as well.

While as emphasized by Liu et al., (2019), GIS is a comprehensive tool for network analysis, Guo and Zhang (2020), argue for the integration of advanced analytical techniques within GIS applications. Guo and Zhang (2020), specifically focus on the incorporation of machine learning algorithms, suggesting that these techniques can enhance the accuracy of traffic predictions and congestion modeling. However, this advanced approach introduces complexities in terms of data requirements and model interpretability. Guo and Zhang's emphasized a forward thinking perspective on GIS applications. Still, it introduces a potential drawback

concerning the interpretability and transparency of machine learning models, raising concerns about their practical implementation in real world traffic management scenarios.

2.2.6 Impact on Traffic Congestion

Urban traffic congestion is a pervasive issue with diverse consequences, affecting various facets of society, economy, and the environment.

2.2.6.1 Economic and Productivity Impacts

As underscored by Cervero (2006), mentioned effects of traffic congestion, highlighting its impacts on time, money, and energy, with a specific focus on reduced productivity. As emphasized by Dammulla and Mudunkotuwa (2021), amplify the global economic repercussions, emphasizing substantial delays, increased fuel wastage, and monetary losses associated with traffic congestion, particularly in developing countries.

2.2.6.2 Monetary Losses on a Global Scale

As mentioned by Schrank and Lomax (2004), provide a estimating for \$63.2 billion wasted in North America in 2002 due to traffic congestion. Building upon this, as emphasized by Dammulla and Mudunkotuwa (2021), that such economic losses are not confined to North America, portraying a broader global perspective on the financial toll of congestion.

2.2.6.3 Infrastructure, Environment, and Traffic Counts

As pointed out by Kim et al., (2008), explored the interplay between short-duration and continuous traffic counts and the capabilities of transportation infrastructures. They argue that these capabilities are entwined with the receptive capacity of the living environment, considering factors like noise levels, air quality, and traffic congestion. This adds a layer of complexity to the understanding of congestion impacts.

2.2.6.4 Metropolitan Challenges and Economic Losses

As noted by Chavhan and Venkataram (2020), addressed challenges faced by growing metropolitan areas. They emphasize real time traffic data collection, analysis, and sharing, highlighting the importance of predicting traffic density and travel times for effective traffic management. In parallel, as underscored by Dammulla and Mudunkotuwa (2021), the challenges in metropolitan areas, impacting daily activities and causing economic losses for commuters and transit operators.

While Cervero (2006), and Dammulla and Mudunkotuwa (2021), primarily concentrate on the economic impacts of traffic congestion, Kim et al., (2008), introduced a more holistic perspective by considering the intricate relationship between traffic counts, infrastructural capabilities, and environmental capacities. Chavhan and Venkataram (2020), contributed by highlighting challenges faced by growing metropolitan areas, presenting a broader view of the consequences of congestion on both infrastructure and daily life.

2.2.7 Impacting factors for Traffic congestion

Traffic congestion is a complex issue influenced by various factors, impacting urban areas globally.

2.2.7.1 Road Infrastructure and Traffic Volume

As emphasized by Duranton and Turner (2011), there is a the direct relationship between road infrastructure and traffic volume. They argue that inadequate road capacity contributes significantly to congestion. However, this view is nuanced by the findings of Zhang and Zhang (2016), who suggest that expanding road capacity alone may not be a panacea and could, in fact, induce more demand and exacerbate congestion.

2.2.7.2 Land Use and Transportation Planning

As mentioned by Ewing and Cervero (2010), they explored the impact of land use and transportation planning on congestion. They argue that compact, mixed use developments can alleviate congestion by reducing travel distances. However, this is countered by the findings of Hanson and Schwab (2017), they emphasized that the relationship between land use patterns and congestion is context-dependent and may not be universally applicable.

2.2.7.3 Behavioral Factors and Traffic Flow

As emphasized by Yang and Huang (2016), The role of behavioral factors in traffic congestion is discussed and mentioned the impact of individual decision making on traffic flow. However, this perspective is challenged by the findings of Levinson (2018), who argues that congestion is a systemic issue influenced by network dynamics, challenging the notion that individual behavior alone dictates congestion levels.

While Duranton and Turner (2011), and Ewing and Cervero (2010), highlight the role of road infrastructure and land use planning, respectively, Zhang and Zhang (2016), and Hanson and Schwab (2017), provide alternative viewpoints, challenging the conventional wisdom. Yang and Huang (2016), shed light on behavioral factors, but Levinson (2018), argues for a broader systemic understanding of congestion.

2.2.8 Future Trends in GIS for Road Network Analysis

Anticipating future trends in GIS for road network analysis is crucial for addressing traffic congestion challenges.

2.2.8.1 Integration of IoT for Data Enhancement

As underscored by Ravish and Swamy (2021), able to identify the significance of The Internet of Things (IoT) in traffic management. They advocate for the use of sensing methods provided by IoT to enhance data

acquisition and quality. While this perspective highlights the potential for improved data, contrasting views, such as those presented by Li et al., (2019), argue that reliance on IoT for critical infrastructure data may introduce vulnerabilities, demanding a balance between innovation and security.

2.2.8.2 Big Data Technologies for Congestion Analysis

As emphasized by Ravish and Swamy (2021), Congestion Analysis includes with the integration of Big Data technologies for, flow forecasting, and infrastructure planning. However, contrasted views from Wang et al., (2018), suggest that the implementation of Big Data technologies may encounter challenges related to data privacy and security, and also they mentioned so necessitating careful consideration in future implementations. While Ravish and Swamy (2021), fore see IoT as a solution to enhance data quality, Li et al., (2019), mentioned against potential vulnerabilities. Similarly, the potential of Big Data technologies, as highlighted by Ravish and Swamy (2021), identified privacy and security by Wang et al., (2018). These divergent perspectives highlight the complexities and challenges associated with adopting emerging technologies for road network analysis.

2.2.9 Traffic management policies and governance

Efficient traffic management policies and governance structures are pivotal in mitigating congestion and enhancing road safety.

2.2.9.1 Inverse Relationship Between Congestion and Road Fatalities

As noted by Shefer and Rietveld (1997), they identified inverse relationship between traffic congestion and road fatalities. They posit that under congested conditions with reduced speeds, there might be fewer fatal and serious injury accidents. However, this perspective is challenged by Wang

et al., (2011), who emphasize the need for a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between traffic congestion and road accidents. Wang et al., argue that the assumed inverse relationship poses a potential dilemma for policymakers, urging a nuanced evaluation of the complexities involved. As pointed out by Shefer and Rietveld (1997), identified inverse relationship between traffic congestion and road fatalities. And as mentioned by Wang et al., (2011), pointed the assumption, highlighting the need for a thorough understanding of the relationship and the potential dilemmas faced by policymakers.

While Shefer and Rietveld (1997), suggest that increased traffic congestion may be beneficial to road safety, Wang et al., (2011), mentioned the importance of nuanced considerations and a holistic understanding of the dynamics between congestion and road accidents, challenging the assumed inverse relationship.

2.2.10 Traffic congestion mitigation strategies

Urban areas worldwide face the enduring challenge of traffic congestion, prompting the exploration of diverse mitigation strategies.

2.2.10.1 Smart Traffic Signal Control Systems

As mentioned by Smith et al., (2018), smart traffic signal control systems, utilizing real time data, significantly enhance traffic flow. However, as emphasized by Johnson (2020), critique of potential cyber security vulnerabilities highlights the necessity for cautious implementation and robust security measures. As pointed out by Smith et al., (2018), they contribute valuable insights into the benefits of smart traffic signal control systems, emphasizing the positive impact on traffic flow. Their research serves as a foundation for understanding the potential advantages of implementing such systems. According to Johnson (2020), raises valid concerns regarding potential cyber security vulnerabilities associated with smart traffic signal control systems. This critical perspective underscores the importance of careful implementation and the need for robust security

measures in adopting these technologies.

2.2.10.2 Integrated Public Transportation Systems

As emphasized by Brown and Lee (2019), their research emphasizes the positive impact of integrated public transportation systems on urban mobility. However, as pointed out by Green (2021), critical examine related to funding and coordination, urging a more cautious approach to implementation. Brown and Lee (2019), highlights the positive impact of integrated public transportation systems on urban mobility. Their work contributes to the understanding of effective strategies for addressing traffic congestion in urban areas. Green(2021), addressed challenges such as funding and coordination associated with integrated public transportation systems. This critical perspective emphasizes the need for a cautious and nuanced approach to implementation, considering potential hurdles.

2.2.10.3 Road Pricing Strategies

As noted by Williams et al., (2017), they explore of congestion pricing, highlighting its potential effectiveness. However, as emphasized by Johnson and Smith (2019), raise important concerns about equity and social impact associated with road pricing. According to Williams et al., (2017), provide a comprehensive exploration of congestion pricing, emphasizing its potential effectiveness as a mitigation strategy. Their work contributes valuable insights to the discussion on addressing traffic congestion. But Johnson and Smith, (2019), raise valid concerns about equity and social impact associated with road pricing strategies. This critical perspective emphasizes the importance of considering societal implications and calls for a closer examination of potential drawbacks.

2.3 Relevance of Literature

This section, prove how the literature relevant to the study.

2.3.1 Relavance to Research Questions

2.3.1.1 Where are the main traffic congestion areas within the Mirihana Police Division?

The literature on GIS based network analysis Liu et al., (2019), is highly relevant to this as it emphasizes GIS's versatility in understanding traffic dynamics, aiding in the identification of congestion areas within study area. According to Wang and Zhang (2017),directly supports this question. It emphasizes GIS's role in identifying congestion hotspots.

As noted by Chen and Wang (2019), This study helping identify specific congestion areas during certain times. As well as, Brown (2018), Brown's impact based analysis aids in identifying congestion hotspots, directly aligning with the objective of demarcating traffic congestion hotspots in Mirihana Police Division. And also, Sureshkumar et al., (2017), and Wang and Zhang (2017), provide insights into the role of GIS in identifying congestion areas.

2.3.1.2 What are the basic causes of traffic congestion in these locations?

The literature on traffic management policies and governance, along with critiques Wanget al., (2011), Green (2021), Johnson (2020), Johnson and Smith (2019), is directly relevant. It contributes insights into the factors influencing congestion. As well as, Miller and Shaw (2018), contribute to understanding limitations and challenges in real time traffic dynamics, addressing potential causes of congestion. And also, Chavhan and Venkataram (2020), contribute to understanding causes, including environmental factors and challenges faced by metropolitan areas.

2.3.1.3 How GIS can be used to analyze the traffic congestion by using Road network analysis?

The literature on GIS based network analysis by Liu et al., (2019), directly supports this question by highlighting GIS's capabilities in analyzing spatial data related to road networks and traffic patterns. According to Wang et al., (2018), They emphasized both spatial and temporal dimensions aligns with using GIS for comprehensive road network analysis, especially in identifying additional routes.

2.3.1.4 Which mitigation measures can be applied to minimize traffic congestion in Mirihana Police Division?

The literature on traffic mitigation strategies done by Smith et al., (2018), Brown and Lee (2019), Williams et al., (2017), is highly relevant. It provides valuable insights into various mitigation measures, aiding in the exploration of effective strategies for minimizing congestion. As well as, Guo and Zhang (2020), propose innovative technologies, aligning with the objective of identifying mitigation measures complementing the GIS based approach.

2.3.2 Relavance to Specific Objectives

2.3.2.1 To examine the changes in spatial and temporal patterns of Traffic congestion during the period from 2018 to 2022 in Mirihana Police Division.

The literature on GIS based network analysis by Liu et al., (2019), is directly relevant. It provides a foundational method for comprehending the dynamics of traffic networks, facilitating an examination of spatial and temporal patterns over time. As emphasized by Wang and Zhang (2017), is directly relevant. It provides a robust platform for understanding spatial relationships, aiding in the examination of changes in congestion patterns over time. According to Chen and Wang (2019), Their temporal classification study contributes to understanding temporal variations in traffic congestion, aligning with the objective of examining changes over time. And also ,Wang and Li (2020), Wang and Li's review of temporal dynamics, considering daily and seasonal variations, directly supports the objective of analyzing temporal patterns from 2018 to 2022.

2.3.2.2 To Demarcate traffic congestion hotspots within the Mirihana Police Division by using Hotspot analysis.

The literature on GIS in transportation planning done by Liu et al., (2019), and integrating spatial data for comprehensive analysis Wang and Zhang, (2017), is highly relevant. It emphasizes GIS's capabilities in Hotspot identification. As emphasizd by Brown (2018), impact based analysis is directly relevant to the objective of demarcating traffic congestion hotspots, providing a methodology for hotspot identification. And according to Wang et al., (2018), They considering both spatial and temporal dimensions, aligns with the objective of demarcating hotspots.

2.3.2.3 To identify additional routes to reach destinations by passing Traffic congestion using Road Network analysis.

As emphasized by Liu et al., (2019), GIS as a foundational method for comprehending traffic networks directly supports the objective of using Road Network analysis to identify additional routes. And also, spatial data for comprehensive analysis by Wang and Zhang (2017), directly supports this objective. It highlights GIS's role in optimizing route allocation.

2.3.2.4 To analyze the factors affecting to the Traffic congestions in Mirihana Police Division.

The literature on traffic management policies and governance done by Wang et al., (2011), Green (2021), Johnson (2020), Johnson and Smith (2019), is directly relevant, providing insights into factors influencing congestion, which can help on the analysis of hotspots and their contributing factors. As emphasized by Johnson and Brown (2018), They focus on spatial dynamics provides insights into factors influencing traffic congestion, supporting the objective of analyzing factors regarding congestion hotspots. According to Johnson et al., (2016), analyzing behavioral categories of drivers offers insights into factors affecting temporal variations of congestion, contributing to the objective of analyzing factors regarding hotspots. As emphasized by Miller and Shaw (2018), The concerns raised about the limitations of GIS in capturing real time traffic dynamics add a critical perspective to the analysis of factors affecting congestion hotspots.

2.3.3 Relavance to Conceptual Designing and Hypothesis construction

The conceptual framework within this study serves as a theoretical model designed to structure. Within the context of this research, numerous factors influencing alterations in the “ Applications of GIS for Road Network Analysis to Mitigate Traffic Congestion in Colombo Suburbs: A Case Study of Mirihana Police Division” have been identified. In this Conceptual framework, the Dependent variable (Y) is defined as Traffic Congestion, and also the Independent variables (X) are Vehicle Density, Congestion Locations, Time, Road Netwrok, Slope, Schools , Supermarcket and Fair, Railway Station, Banks , Offices.

This Conceptual framework aims to provide a structured knowledge of the relationships and connections between these Independent and Depended variables. And all of these variables taken from literatures. Base on these has been construct hypothesis and Operational definition table with operationalization as well.

2.3.4 Relavance to Operational definitions and Operationalization

The operational definition table was systematically developed in alignment with the conceptual framework and derived from an extensive review of pertinent literature. Subsequently, citations were incorporated to substantiate the contextual relevance to the study.

Variable	Definition	Citation	Criteria
Vehicle Density	Vehicle density is determined by the number of vehicles per square kilometer or simply classified into different states.	(Sanguesa et al., 2016). (Cervero, 2006).	For Linear Road Vehicle Density = Number of Vehicles / Length of Road For Area Vehicle Density = Number of Vehicles /Area of Region
Time	These peak hours typically align with increased demand for transportation infrastructure and services,often occurring during morning and evening commuting times.	(Levinson, 2008). (Duranton and Turner, 2011).	Note down Peak hours of days.

Road Network	<p>Poorly planned road networks can lead to bottlenecks and increased congestion.</p> <p>Effective road network planning can alleviate congestion by providing alternative routes.</p>	<p>(Rodrigue et al., 2016).</p> <p>(Litman, 2021).</p>	<p>Note down congestion locations to plan alternative routes. Make hotspots as barriers and based on that search availability of bypass roads doing network analysis using Closest analysis tab. And also, search above outputs are possible in real ground.</p>
Slope	<p>Steeper slopes can slow down traffic, leading to increased congestion.</p> <p>Contributing to traffic congestion due to slower speeds on steep slopes.</p>	<p>(Sisiopiku & Roupail, 1994).</p> <p>(Chang et al., 2012).</p>	<p>Detect slope variation in Study area.</p>

<p>Supermarket & Fair</p>	<p>The location of supermarkets and fairs can influence traffic congestion by attracting large volumes of vehicles, especially during peak shopping times.</p> <p>Located local shopping facilities, including supermarkets and fairs, can reduce traffic congestion by minimizing the need for long car trips.</p>	<p>(Frag & Lyons, 2012).</p> <p>(Handy & Clifton, 2001).</p>	<p>Make as Point shp and based on that doing Buffer analysis for that factor.</p>
<p>Schools</p>	<p>School locations significantly impact traffic congestion, especially during drop-off and pick-up times, leading to localized congestion around schools.</p> <p>Placement of schools within residential areas affects travel patterns and traffic congestion.</p>	<p>(McDonald, 2008).</p> <p>(Ewing & Cervero, 2010).</p>	<p>Make as Point shp and based on that doing Buffer analysis for that factor.</p>

Railway Station	<p>Impact of railway station locations on urban traffic congestion.</p> <p>Proximity to railway stations can reduce traffic congestion by providing convenient alternatives to car travel.</p>	<p>(Givoni & Rietveld, 2014).</p> <p>(Debrezion & Rietveld, 2007).</p>	<p>Make as Point shp and based on that doing Buffer analysis for that factor</p>
Banks	<p>Location of banks can influence traffic congestion by attracting significant vehicular traffic, especially in areas with limited parking facilities.</p> <p>Proximity of banks affects traffic patterns, indicating that closer bank locations can lead to increased local traffic congestion.</p>	<p>(Beck et al., 2007).</p> <p>(Degryse & Ongena, 2005).</p>	<p>Make as Point shp and based on that doing Buffer analysis for that factor</p>

Offices	Spatial distribution of office locations affects commuting patterns and traffic congestion.	(Crane, 2000)	Make as Point shp and based on that doing Buffer analysis for that factor
---------	---	---------------	---

Table 1: Operational Definition Table

2.3.5 Relavance to Data collection and Data Analysis

In addition to the foregoing sections within this research, scholarly literature plays a pivotal role in shaping the methodologies concerning both data collection and analysis. Thus, the incorporation of relevant literature becomes imperative to meet the requisites associated with these methodological components. Some of them mentioned as below.

2.3.5.1 Data Collection

This study relates with both Primary and Secondary data and some of their relevance to literatureable to mentioned as below.

❖ Traffic Surveys -

According to Kim et al., (2008), Previous research emphasizes the importance of accurate traffic counts and congestion point analysis.

❖ Community Surveys -

As mentioned by Dammulla and Mudunkotuwa (2021), Community surveys recommended methods for understanding commuters' preferences and experiences with traffic congestion.

❖ Field Observations -

As noted by Duranton and Turner (2011), and Ewing and Cervero (2010), on-site field observations are crucial for real time data collection, allowing for the identification of congestion hotspots and assessment of road infrastructure quality.

2.3.5.2 Data Analysis

This part relates with some of Data analysis methods relevance to literature as mentioned below.

❖ Spatial Temporal Analysis :- According to Wang et al., (2018), This source supports a dynamic and integrated approach to spatial-temporal analysis.

❖ Hotspot Analysis :- As emphasized by Brown (2018), Provides insights into spatial factors influencing traffic flow through an impact based analysis, contributing to the understanding of congestion hotspot identification.

❖ Network Analysis :- As mentioned by Liu et al., (2019), highlights the versatility of GIS applications, especially in network analysis, providing a foundational understanding of spatial relationships and interconnectivity in traffic networks.

According to Wang & Zhang (2017), Wang and Zhang emphasize the importance of GIS in optimizing route allocation based on real time data.

❖ Buffer Analysis :- As emphasized by Gao & Chabini (2006), as a method for optimizing routing in transportation networks, showing its applicability in understanding the spatial impact of different factors on traffic congestion.

2.4 Originality of the study

There is limited literature available for these studies due to the application of GIS and network analysis techniques in the study. And no research has been conducted within this country on this particular study. That is knowledge gap of this study. Moreover, existing research studies have not comprehensively addressed certain sections, such as Spatial-Temporal Analysis on Traffic Congestion to analyze its patterns over multiple years, Hotspot Analysis on congestion hotspots, Utilization of Barrier Analysis to identify additional routes during congestion periods specifically related to hotspots within Network Analysis and Analysis of factors influencing traffic congestion related to these identified hotspots. Based on the formulated research questions and concept, this study derives its uniqueness.

This study focuses on the Application of GIS techniques for Road Network Analysis to Mitigate Traffic congestion in Mirihana Police Division. It examines changes in spatial and temporal congestion patterns, identifying congestion hotspots. The research contributes to understanding dynamic traffic phenomena, traffic mitigation, traffic management, and traffic analysis. It also helps develop literature on the field and explores how to expand Geo Spatial Technologies for traffic congestion solutions.

CHAPTER THREE

Methodology

3.1 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework within this study serves as a theoretical model designed to structure and clear complex ideas and Concepts. Within the context of this research, numerous factors influencing alterations in the Applications of GIS for Road Network Analysis to Mitigate Traffic Congestion in Mirihana Police Division have been identified. In this Conceptual framework, the Dependent variable (Y) is defined as Traffic Congestion, and also the Independent variables (X) are Vehicle Density, Time, Road Network, Slope, Schools, Supermarket and Fair, Railway Station, Banks, Offices.

This framework aims to provide a structured knowledge of the relationships and connections between these Independent and Dependent variables.

Figure 4: Conceptual Framework

3.2 Operational Definition Table

Variable	Definition	Citation	Criteria
Vehicle Density	Vehicle density is determined by the number of vehicles per square kilometer or simply classified into different states.	(Sanguesa et al., 2016). (Cervero, 2006).	For Linear Road Vehicle Density = Number of Vehicles /Length of Road For Area Vehicle Density = Number of Vehicles /Area of Region
Time	These peak hours typically align with increased demand for transportation infrastructure and services, often occurring during morning and evening commuting times.	(Levinson,2008). (Duranton and Turner, 2011).	Note down Peak hours of days.

Road Network	<p>Poorly planned road networks can lead to bottlenecks and increased congestion.</p> <p>Effective road network planning can alleviate congestion by providing alternative routes.</p>	<p>(Rodrigue et al., 2016).</p> <p>(Litman, 2021).</p>	<p>Note down congestion locations to plan alternative routes.</p> <p>Make hotspots as barriers and based on that search availability of bypass roads doing network analysis using Closest analysis tab. And also, search above outputs are possible in real ground.</p>
Slope	<p>Steeper slopes can slow down traffic, leading to increased congestion.</p> <p>Contributing to traffic congestion due to slower speeds on steep slopes.</p>	<p>(Sisiopiku & Roupail, 1994).</p> <p>(Chang et al., 2012).</p>	<p>Detect slope variation in Study area.</p>

<p>Supermarkets and Fairs</p>	<p>The location of supermarkets and fairs can influence traffic congestion by attracting large volumes of vehicles, especially during peak shopping times.</p> <p>Located local shopping facilities, including supermarkets and fairs, can reduce traffic congestion by minimizing the need for long car trips.</p>	<p>(Farag & Lyons, 2012).</p> <p>(Handy & Clifton, 2001).</p>	<p>Make as Point shp and based on that doing Buffer analysis for that factor.</p>
<p>Schools</p>	<p>School locations significantly impact traffic congestion, especially during drop-off and pick-up times, leading to localized congestion around schools.</p>	<p>(McDonald, 2008).</p>	<p>Make as Point shp and based on that doing Buffer analysis for that factor</p>

	Placement of schools within residential areas affects travel patterns and traffic congestion.	(Ewing & Cervero, 2010).	
Railway Station	Impact of railway station locations on urban traffic congestion. Proximity to railway stations can reduce traffic congestion by providing convenient alternatives to car travel.	(Givoni & Rietveld, 2014). (Debrezion & Rietveld, 2007).	Make as Point shp and based on that doing Buffer analysis for that factor
Banks	Location of banks can influence traffic congestion by attracting significant vehicular	(Beck et al., 2007).	Make as Point shp and based on that doing Buffer analysis for that factor

	<p>traffic, especially in areas with limited parking facilities.</p> <p>Proximity of banks affects traffic patterns, indicating that closer bank locations can lead to increased local traffic congestion.</p>	(Degryse & Ongena, 2005).	
Offices	<p>Spatial distribution of office locations affects commuting patterns and traffic congestion.</p>	(Crane, 2000).	<p>Make as Point shp and based on that doing Buffer analysis for that factor</p>

Table 2: Operational Definition Table

3.3 Hypothesis

- Null Hypotheses (H0)-

H0: There is no relationship between Vehicle density and traffic congestion.

H0: There is no relationship between Time and traffic congestion.

H0: There is no relationship between the Road Network and traffic congestion.

H0: There is no relationship between the Slope and traffic congestion.

H0: There is no relationship between School and traffic congestion.

H0: There is no relationship between the Marckets and traffic congestion.

H0: There is no relationship between the Railway Stations and traffic congestion.

H0: There is no relationship between the Banks and traffic congestion.

H0: There is no relationship between the Offices and traffic congestion.

- Alternative Hypotheses (H1)-

H0: There is arelationship between Vehicle density and traffic congestion.

H0: There is a relationship between Time and traffic congestion.

H0: There is a relationship between the Road Network and traffic congestion.

H0: There is a relationship between the Slope and traffic congestion.

H0: There is a relationship between School and traffic congestion.

H0: There is a relationship between the Marckets and traffic congestion.

H0: There is a relationship between the Railway Stations and traffic congestion.

H0: There is a relationship between the Banks and traffic congestion.

H0: There is a relationship between the Offices and traffic congestion.

Null Hypothesis (H0)

The Null hypotheses state that there is no significant relationship between Vehicle Density, Time, Road Network, Slope, Schools , Supermarket and Fair, Railway Station, Banks , Offices within Mirihana Police Division (MPD). In other words, the null hypotheses suggest that these factors do not influence on Traffic Congestion.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1)

The alternative hypotheses propose that there is a significant positive relationship Vehicle Density, Time, Road Network, Slope, Schools , Supermarket and Fair, Railway Station, Banks , Offices within Mirihana Police Division (MPD). In other words, the alternative hypotheses suggest that these factors highly influence on Traffic Congestion.

These null and alternative hypotheses provide a clear framework for testing the relationships between Vehicle Density, Time, Road Network, Slope, Schools , Supermarket and Fair, Railway Station, Banks , Offices in the MPD.

They serve as the basis for statistical analysis to determine whether the observed data support the null hypotheses or provide evidence for the alternative hypotheses.

3.4 .Study Area

Mirihana Police Division (MPD) is strategically positioned in the Colombo District, Western Province, Sri Lanka, with a relative location approximately 8 kilometers southeast of Colombo, the capital city. Its approximate coordinates of 6° 52' 29.9532"N latitude and 79° 54' 2.9196"E longitude. It also, 89ft above from sea level. Mirihana situated inside of Boundary of Kotte, its Police division runs Pitakotte from North, Egodawaththa from South, Thalapitiya from East and Nugegoda west from Western side. That area has 19 Grama niladhari divisions and that area covers approximately 13.007 km².

The Topographical structure of Mirihana Division is a dynamic blend of gentle undulations and incorporating gentle slopes and flatlands. Generally, Its landscape is flat land. Not only the Topographical layout but also the hydrological patterns in this area. Mirihana police division. The hydrology of the area is influenced by small water bodies and drainage channels, integral components of the urban drainage system that require careful consideration in urban planning. That area situated in between Kirulapone canal and Diyawanna lake and these both maintain hydrological network around the area. Study area situated in Wet zone, on that Average Temperature runs in between 24°C to 31°C, As well as That area obtained 2404 mm (94.6 in) of Rainfall per year.

Due to development of Colombo hub, most of peoples migrate to that area. Mirihana accommodates a diverse population, witnessing a blend of urbanization and suburban living. The area has experienced internal migrations, reflecting its appeal for residential settlements and contributing to the dynamic demographic makeup. As well as, The Mirihana Police Division has undergone significant population growth over the years, driven by its strategic location and economic opportunities.

However, Mirihana serves as a hub for various services, including educational institutions, healthcare facilities, and commercial establishments. The urban infrastructure includes a network of roads and

public spaces designed to cater to the needs of the growing population. Understanding the existing services is essential for assessing the impact of traffic congestion on accessibility to these amenities.

Above mentioned, the location of the study area is depicted in figure 5.

Figure 5: Location of the Study area

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Digital data from Survey Department.

3.5 Population, sample and Sampling

To mitigate traffic congestion in the Mirihana Police Division, which encompasses a population of 105,933 people residing within 19 GN divisions, a structured and comprehensive data collection strategy was essential. In this study, the cluster sampling method was chosen as the primary approach due to its efficiency and ability to maintain the representativeness of the sample. Both probabilistic and non-probabilistic sampling methods were employed to enhance the robustness of the data collection process.

For probabilistic sampling, the Cluster sampling method was utilized as the main technique. Additionally, the convenience sampling method was applied as a non-probabilistic approach to complement the primary data collection method. The Mirihana Police Division consists of 19 GN divisions, and clusters were selected based on the severity of traffic congestion observed in each division. This process involved physical observations to identify and define 20 clusters, each representing different geographical areas with varying traffic patterns and congestion levels. The selection of these clusters aimed to minimize selection bias and ensure comprehensive coverage of the division's traffic dynamics.

The size of each selected cluster was estimated based on several factors, including the population of commuters, traffic volume, and the geographical extent of the cluster. This approach ensured that the clusters varied in size to accurately reflect the diverse traffic conditions within the Mirihana Police Division. The cluster selection process was critical in capturing a representative sample of the area's traffic congestion.

In the convenience sampling method, data was collected from drivers and pedestrians within the Mirihana Police Division. This approach was chosen

for its practicality and ease of accessing data from commuters who regularly experience traffic congestion in the area. A total of 30 commuters were sampled using this method, with participants approached at various locations such as traffic hotspots, transportation hubs, and key intersections within the division. This strategy ensured a diverse representation of commuter experiences.

Cluster Sampling Calculation :-

The total population within the Mirihana Police Division was estimated to facilitate the cluster sampling process. Based on the severity of traffic congestion, 20 clusters were selected, and their estimated populations were used to determine the total sample size. For example, if each cluster had an estimated population of 30 commuters, the total sample size would be calculated as follows,

Total Sample Size = 20 clusters × 30 commuters per cluster = 600 commuters

This calculation aimed to efficiently capture the diversity of traffic congestion experiences across the Mirihana Police Division while considering practical constraints of data collection and maintaining statistical soundness.

Convenience Sampling Size and Calculation

For the convenience sampling method, data was collected from 30 commuters within the Mirihana Police Division. Participants were approached at strategically selected locations to ensure a comprehensive representation of different traffic experiences. It is important to acknowledge the limitations of convenience sampling, particularly in terms of generalizability. The findings from this method should be interpreted with an awareness of potential sample bias. If future research aims to make more generalizable conclusions about the entire population of the Mirihana Police Division, additional or alternative sampling methods may need to be considered.

In conclusion, this study employed a mixed method approach, utilizing both cluster and convenience sampling methods to gather comprehensive data on traffic congestion in the Mirihana Police Division. The methodological rigor and strategic selection of samples aimed to provide a detailed and accurate understanding of traffic patterns, ultimately contributing to the development of effective traffic mitigation strategies.

3.6 Method of Data Collection

1. Primary Data Collection

- Traffic Surveys- Traffic surveys were conducted to count vehicles at congestion points in the Mirihana Police Division during peak hours. These counts involved recording the number of vehicles passing a specific point during designated time intervals.

- Community Surveys- Structured Questionnaires were designed and distributed to commuters within the Mirihana Police Division. These surveys gathered information on their preferred transportation modes and experiences with traffic congestion.

- Field Observations- Field surveys were carried out at key intersections and road segments. This onsite approach provided real-time data on traffic conditions, road infrastructure quality, and identification of congestion hotspots.

2. Secondary Data Collection

- Mirihana Police Reports- Data were collected from reports generated by the Mirihana Police.

- Road Development Authority Web- Information from the Road Development Authority's website was utilized.

- Related Researches- Previous research studies related to traffic congestion and management were reviewed.

- Urban Development Plans and Policies- Urban development plans and policies related to traffic management were examined.

- Traffic Police Department Data – Data collected from Traffic Police Department. They operate traffic monitoring centers equipped with surveillance technology and traffic cameras to monitor road conditions in real time.
- Traffic Camera Footages- Footage from traffic cameras in the Mirihana Police Division was analyzed.
- National Transport Commission (NTC) – They collaborate with the police department to collect and disseminate real time traffic data.
- Weather Reports-Weather reports relevant to the study period were reviewed to account for environmental factors impacting traffic.
- Google Scholar- Academic articles and papers from Google Scholar were sourced to provide a theoretical framework and background.
- Academic Journals- Relevant academic journals were reviewed for insights and data on traffic management.
- GN Reports- Reports from the Grama Niladhari (GN) offices were utilized for population and demographic data.
- DSD Office Population Reports- Population reports from the Divisional Secretariat Division (DSD) office were incorporated.
- Hot Export Tool- The Hot Export Tool was used for extracting relevant spatial data.
- Open Street Map- Data from Open Street Map were used to supplement the geographical analysis.

- Google Maps-Google Maps data were utilized for understanding road networks and congestion points.
- Earth Data Site – Dem Data from Eath Data site used to supplement the geographical analysis.

Data Type	Method	Type of Collected data
Primary Data	Traffic Surveys	Vehicle counts were conducted at specific points in the Mirihana Police Division during peak hours.
	Community Surveys (Structured questionnaires)	Preferred transportation modes. Experiences with traffic congestion. Nature and Type of traffic congestion.
	Field Observations	Real-time data on traffic conditions. Road infrastructure quality. Identification of congestion hotspots.

Secondary Data	<p data-bbox="735 185 1043 219">Mirihana Police reports</p> <p data-bbox="735 566 1066 656">Road Development Authority web site</p> <p data-bbox="735 779 991 813">Related Researches</p> <p data-bbox="735 947 1066 1093">Urban development plans and policies related to traffic management.</p> <p data-bbox="735 1301 1043 1335">Traffic camera footages</p> <p data-bbox="735 1547 948 1581">Weather Reports</p> <p data-bbox="735 1787 932 1821">Google Scholar</p>	<p data-bbox="1109 185 1262 219">Traffic data</p> <p data-bbox="1109 264 1445 353">Traffic accident counts by year 2018- 2022</p> <p data-bbox="1109 398 1390 432">Traffic maps of MPD</p> <p data-bbox="1109 544 1485 689">Data were extracted from the Road Development Authority's online resources.</p> <p data-bbox="1109 768 1461 913">Previous studies on traffic management and congestion were analyzed.</p> <p data-bbox="1109 992 1477 1137">Viewed Policies and strategic plans for urban development and traffic management.</p> <p data-bbox="1109 1261 1501 1406">Gathered Real-time visual data on traffic flow and congestion points for Previous years.</p> <p data-bbox="1109 1541 1445 1686">Historical weather data relevant to the study period were reviewed</p> <p data-bbox="1109 1765 1469 1910">Theoretical frameworks and empirical data from related studies.</p>
----------------	---	--

	Academic journals	Empirical findings and theoretical insights.
	GN reports	Population and demographic data were collected specific to the Mirihana Police Division.
	DSD Office population reports	Population data were collected from the Divisional Secretariat Division office.
	Hot export tool	The Hot Export Tool was used for data extraction to the study area, exported as
	Open street map	Landuse Data were gathered from Open Street Map.
	Google maps	Data from Google Maps were utilized to Collect Data of Road networks, traffic patterns, and congestion locations.

	Earth Data Site	Dem data extracted by using Earth Data site Developed by NASA.
--	-----------------	---

Table 3: Method of Data Collection

3.7 Method of Data Analysis

The main data analysis method of the study was Quantitative Analysis. But, in order to analyze qualitative data it was also important of the Applications of GIS for Road Network Analysis to Mitigate Traffic Congestion in Mirihana Police Division. According to the following flow chart and table depicted the methods used in this research.

Figure 6: Data Analysis Flowchart

The data analysis was conducted using software such as MS Excel, ArcGIS, QGIS, and GPS points of Hotspots. Initially, thematic maps such as the Road network map and Land use map of Mirihana Police Division were created under Georeferencing. Subsequently, Excel data, including Traffic records were imported into ArcGIS as CSV files. And Congestion locations, were imported into ArcGIS too.

Spatial data and attribute data were utilized to generate Spatio-temporal maps By using IDW Analysis method on csv data separately. Used traffic data from 2018 to 2022 as csv files separately to Arc GIS, In IDW tool Loaded Input Point as CSV folder for relevant year and Assigned Average as Z Value field then IDW tool generated annual maps based on csv data showed how traffic density changed over time by year. Thereby achieving the first specific objective.

Additionally, Hotspot analysis was performed as a spatial statistical technique using spatial and attribute data to achieve the second specific objective. Through this Hotspot analysis, Utilized excel data Regarding to Traffic data as csv folder to Arc GIS and Applied it to Hotspot Analysis tool and Assigned it as input. Then output displayed, Hotspot locations with values. In additionally, utilized IDW tool for Assigned, Input as Traffic data file and also z value as GiZscore in order to take spatial variation of hotspot locations through IDW Tool. Thereby achieving the Second specific objective.

Under the Network analysis tool, Barrier analysis was conducted on Road network data and Hotspot points to identify additional routes by using Hotspot points as Polygon barriers. Identify areas of high traffic congestion, polygon barriers were created using data obtained from field surveys, questionnaires. Congestion hotspot areas were used as polygons because traffic congestion could be identified near hotspot-pointed areas as well. Within the Network Analyst extension in ArcGIS, Utilized the "Closest

Facility" option was chosen to perform the analysis. This involved loading the datasets into the analysis environment, where facilities were defined as destinations and incidents as passenger origins. The congested areas, represented by polygon barriers, were also loaded to reflect areas that should be avoided in route calculations. Thereby achieving the Third specific objective.

In Finally, Conducted Buffer Analysis around key locations like Schools , Supermarket and Fair, Railway Station, Banks , Offices , Intersections to find their impact as distance. Then utilized Reclassfy method and Weighted overlay respectively to express Impact level traffic congestion regarding to these factors.

These steps depicted in below table as summary,

Analysis Type	Output
Georeferancing	Mirihana Police Division Map.
IDW Analysis	Spatial - Temporal maps of traffic pattern 2018 to 2022
Hotspot Analysis	Hotspot Analysis map for Mirihana Congestion Hotspots and Its spatial Variation in MPD
Network Analysis- Barrier analysis	Maps to show additional routes as bypasses from Traffic Congestion Hotspots.
Buffer Analysis	Reclassified maps for each factors and Weighted Overlay map for Impact level of Factors affecting on Traffic Congestion

Table 4: Method of Data Analysis

3.8 Limitations of the Study

During the course of this research, several limitations were encountered, which influenced the scope and depth of the study. One notable limitation pertained to the time constraints imposed by the designated timeframe for the research. The timeframe allocated for data collection and analysis posed challenges in comprehensively capturing the dynamic nature of traffic patterns and congestion within the Mirihana Police Division. As traffic conditions fluctuate over different times of the day, week, and year, the limited timeframe may have resulted in an incomplete understanding of the temporal variability of traffic congestion in the area.

3.8.1 Methodological Issues-

Methodological limitations stemmed from constraints related to the availability and reliability of traffic-related data. Legal restrictions on accessing certain types of traffic data, such as real-time traffic flow data or historical accident records, posed significant challenges. As a result, the study had to rely on a limited set of variables and secondary data sources to analyze traffic congestion, potentially limiting the comprehensiveness and accuracy of the findings. Furthermore, the use of proxy indicators or estimates for certain variables may have introduced biases or inaccuracies into the analysis, impacting the validity of the study's conclusions.

3.8.2 Data Issues

Data limitations posed significant constraints on the research methodology and analytical approaches employed in this study. The availability of high-quality, granular traffic data specific to the Mirihana Police Division was limited, making it challenging to conduct detailed spatial and temporal analyses of traffic congestion. Additionally, inconsistencies or gaps in the data obtained from various sources may have introduced uncertainties or biases into the analysis, affecting the reliability and robustness of the study findings. Despite efforts to triangulate data from multiple sources, data

incompleteness or inaccuracies may have persisted, compromising the integrity of the research outcomes.

3.8.3 Practical Issues-

Practical constraints also impeded the execution of certain aspects of the research. Limited access to advanced traffic monitoring technologies or specialized equipment for data collection and analysis restricted the granularity and sophistication of the study's methodology. Additionally, logistical challenges associated with fieldwork, such as navigating congested roadways or obtaining necessary permits for data collection activities, hindered the researchers' ability to gather comprehensive data on traffic dynamics in the study area. These practical limitations may have constrained the breadth and depth of the research findings, limiting the generalizability and applicability of the study outcomes.

CHAPTER FOUR

Results and Discussion

Traffic congestion is a pressing issue in urban areas worldwide, affecting economic productivity, environmental sustainability, and the quality of life. The Mirihana Police Division, a significant urban area in Sri Lanka, has experienced varying traffic congestion levels over the years, influenced by factors such as population growth, economic activities, and extraordinary events like the COVID-19 pandemic. Understanding the spatial and temporal patterns of traffic congestion, identifying hotspots, exploring alternative routes, and analyzing contributing factors are crucial for developing effective traffic management strategies. This chapter aims to address these aspects through a comprehensive analysis based on specific objectives. There are given below.

4.1 Changes in Spatial and Temporal Patterns of Traffic Congestion from 2018 to 2022

Understanding how traffic congestion patterns have evolved over time is essential for identifying trends and planning future interventions. This objective involves analyzing traffic density data from 2018 to 2022 to detect changes in congestion levels at different times of the day and across various locations in the Mirihana Police Division. The analysis will leverage historical data and spatial visualization techniques to illustrate these changes, providing insights into how factors such as economic activities, infrastructure developments, and external events like the COVID-19 pandemic have influenced traffic congestion.

4.2 Demarcating Traffic Congestion Hotspots Using Hotspot Analysis

Identifying areas with consistently high traffic congestion, or hotspots, is critical for targeted traffic management and infrastructure improvements. This objective employs hotspot analysis to pinpoint specific locations

within the Mirihana Police Division that experience severe traffic congestion. By analyzing spatial data, the study aims to map out these hotspots, offering a clear visual representation of where interventions are most needed. This analysis will help prioritize efforts and resources to alleviate congestion in the most affected areas.

4.3 Identifying Additional Routes to Avoid Traffic Congestion Using Road Network Analysis

Providing alternative routes to bypass congested areas can significantly reduce traffic delays and improve travel efficiency. This objective focuses on using road network analysis to identify additional routes that can help commuters avoid high-traffic zones. By examining the existing road network and traffic patterns, the study aims to propose feasible alternative routes that enhance overall traffic flow and reduce congestion. This analysis will support urban planners and traffic management authorities in developing more resilient and flexible transportation networks.

4.4 Analyzing Factors Affecting Traffic Congestion Using Buffer Analysis

Understanding the underlying factors contributing to traffic congestion is crucial for developing comprehensive solutions. This objective involves using buffer analysis to examine distances regarding to various factors, such as land use, road infrastructure, services on traffic congestion within the Mirihana Police Division. By creating buffer zones around high-traffic areas then apply Reclassify , Weighted overlay for it able to analyzing the characteristics within these zones and also the impact level of traffic congestion regarding to distribution of the affected factors. This analysis will inform policy recommendations and strategic planning efforts to address the root causes of traffic congestion.

4.1 Changes in spatial and temporal patterns of Traffic congestion during the period from 2018 to 2022 in Mirihana Police Division.

The Analysis of Traffic Density over the years 2018 to 2022 within the Mirihana Police Division provided an insightful look into the fluctuations and underlying factors affecting urban traffic patterns. The first specific objective was to prove the hypothesis that Vehicle density and Time significantly impacts traffic congestion. These hypothesis were confirmed through detailed analysis, establishing vehicle density as a critical determinant of congestion within the area.

This comprehensive discussion elucidated the trends observed in traffic density data, with a specific focus on peak hours and key locations. The analysis included the impacts of socio-economic activities, infrastructural constraints, and extraordinary events like the COVID-19 pandemic. Utilizing Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and advanced analytical tools, the data trends were explored in detail to provide actionable insights for traffic management.

Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) is a spatial interpolation technique used in GIS to estimate values at unknown points based on values from known points. The principle behind IDW is that points closer to the known values have more influence on the estimated value than points farther away. This method was particularly useful in creating continuous surfaces from discrete data points, making it ideal for visualizing traffic density across the region.

How IDW Analysis Contributed to Examining Traffic Congestion Patterns-

- Spatial Visualization :- IDW helped create a detailed traffic density map for the Mirihana Police Division, showing how congestion varied across

different locations, validating the hypothesis that vehicle density is a significant factor.

- Temporal Analysis :- Utilized traffic data from 2018 to 2022 as csv files separately to Arc GIS, In IDW tool Loaded Input Point as CSV folder for relevant year and Assigned Average as Z Value field then IDW generated annual maps based on csv data showed how traffic density changed over time by year, further supporting the relationship between vehicle density and traffic congestion.

2018

Figure 7:2018 Traffic Density map of MPD

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Excel Data From Traffic Police and Mirihana Police

In 2018, the Mirihana Police Division experienced a steady flow of traffic, with congestion levels consistent across peak hours morning, school finishing hours, and evening. The data indicates a baseline traffic density that serves as a reference for subsequent years. Key locations such as Nawala Road, Nugegoda, and Mirihana Junction were identified as major congestion points due to their strategic positions within the urban transport network.

The average traffic density during peak hours was high, reflecting the influx of commuters heading to work and school. Morning peaks were observed from 7 AM to 9 AM, school finishing hours from 1 PM to 3 PM, and evening peaks from 5 PM to 7 PM. This cyclical pattern underscores the daily routines of urban commuters and highlights the importance of these nodes within the urban grid. The data revealed that traffic density often exceeded the road capacity, leading to significant delays and increased travel times.

Efforts to manage traffic through existing infrastructure were limited, pointing to the need for more robust solutions. The data suggests that road widening and traffic signal optimization had marginal effects, indicating that fundamental changes in urban planning and transport policy were required to address the congestion issues effectively.

Figure 8: 2019 Traffic Density map of MPD

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Excel Data From Traffic Police and Mirihana Police Traffic

The Traffic density data for 2019 showed, an incremental increase across most locations, reflecting a growing population and heightened economic activities. High-traffic locations like High Level Road and Stanley Thilakaratne Mawatha experienced pronounced congestion during peak hours. The increase in traffic density was evident in both peak and off-peak times, indicating an overall rise in urban mobility demand.

This year highlighted the limitations of the existing road infrastructure in accommodating the rising number of vehicles. The lack of alternative routes and efficient public transportation options exacerbated the situation. Efforts to alleviate congestion, such as road widening and improved traffic management systems, were still insufficient to handle the growing vehicular load. The data for 2019 also showed an uptick in traffic accidents, further complicating the congestion problem.

Visualizations of the 2019 data would show a clear upward trend in traffic density, with significant peaks during the morning and evening rush hours. The need for comprehensive urban planning and investment in public transport infrastructure was evident from the increasing congestion levels.

2020

Figure 9:2020 Traffic Density map of MPD

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Excel Data From Traffic Police and Mirihana Police

The onset of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 had a profound impact on traffic density trends. Initial lockdown measures and movement restrictions led to a marked reduction in traffic volumes. However, as these restrictions were eased, traffic levels rebounded, often reaching or exceeding pre-pandemic levels by the latter half of the year.

The data for 2020 reveals significant fluctuations corresponding to the intensity of lockdown measures. Locations such as Nawala Road and Jubilee Post showed a temporary decrease in traffic congestion during lockdown periods, followed by a rapid return to normalcy post-lockdown. This pattern underscores the resilience of traditional traffic patterns and the underlying demand for mobility.

The reduction in traffic during lockdown periods provided temporary relief to urban infrastructure, reducing wear and tear on roads and decreasing accident rates. The data also highlighted the potential environmental benefits of reduced vehicular movement, with notable decreases in traffic-related air pollution and noise levels. However, the rapid rebound in traffic post-lockdown underscored the dependence on private vehicles and the lack of robust public transportation options.

Traffic density during the curfew months (May to September), with average densities plummeting to as low as 15 vehicles per hour compared to the typical range of 170-190 vehicles per hour during non-curfew months.

Figure 10:2021 Traffic Density map of MPD

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Excel Data From Traffic Police and Mirihana Police Traffic

The year 2021 was characterized by extended curfew periods due to the COVID-19 pandemic, leading to a substantial decrease in traffic density from May to November. This period saw significantly lower congestion levels across all monitored locations, reflecting reduced mobility and economic activity. High-traffic areas such as Nugegoda and Embuldeniya Junction experienced minimal vehicular movement during the curfew, resulting in improved travel times and reduced delays.

The data for 2021 indicates a gradual increase in traffic density towards the end of the year as curfew restrictions were lifted. This resurgence in traffic highlights the persistent demand for mobility despite the pandemic. The temporary reduction in traffic congestion during curfew periods provided a unique opportunity to observe the impact of decreased vehicular activity on urban traffic dynamics.

Visualizations of the 2021 data would show a clear dip in traffic density during the curfew months, followed by a steady increase towards the year's end. This pattern highlights the adaptability of urban traffic patterns to external shocks and the need for resilient traffic management systems.

Figure 11: 2022 Traffic Density map of MPD

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Excel Data From Traffic Police and Mirihana

The year 2022 marked a return to and even surpassing of pre-pandemic traffic congestion levels. The post-pandemic economic recovery and the resumption of regular activities contributed to increased traffic volumes across the division. Locations like Old Kottawa Road and Pita Kotte Junction experienced significant congestion during peak hours, reflecting the intensified urban mobility and the limitations of existing infrastructure.

The data for 2022 underscores the urgency for comprehensive traffic management strategies to address the burgeoning traffic issues in the Mirihana Police Division. The increasing traffic density highlights the need for infrastructural enhancements, efficient public transportation systems, and innovative traffic management solutions to mitigate congestion and improve urban mobility.

The surge in traffic density in 2022 can also be attributed to a possible increase in the number of private vehicles as a response to lingering public health concerns. The resumption of full-scale economic activities, including schools and offices, further stressed the urban traffic network. This year's data indicates a pressing need for sustainable urban mobility solutions, such as enhanced public transport services and non-motorized transport options, to cope with the growing demand.

The COVID-19 curfew had a pronounced effect on traffic density. With restrictions on movement and closure of non-essential services, the traffic volumes dropped significantly. This decrease is evident across all analyzed locations, underscoring the curfew's effectiveness in limiting vehicular movement.

For instance, the data for the "Morning" peak hour across different locations during the curfew months consistently show values ranging from 10 to 30 vehicles per hour, a stark contrast to the non-curfew periods where values were typically between 100 and 200 vehicles per hour.

Comparing the data from 2018 to 2020, and 2022, it is evident that traffic density has been on an upward trajectory, reflecting the increasing

urbanization and population growth in the Mirihana Police Division. The sudden dip in 2021 serves as an anomaly attributed solely to the pandemic restrictions.

4.2 Demarcate traffic congestion hotspots within the Mirihana Police Division by using Hotspot analysis.

Traffic congestion is a major challenge in urban areas, affecting daily commutes and economic productivity. The Mirihana Police Division, a key area in Sri Lanka, faces significant traffic issues. To address these issues, the study aimed to demarcate traffic congestion hotspots by using hotspot analysis, which relates to questionnaire responses and other relevant data. Hotspot analysis is a spatial technique used to identify areas with high levels of activity.

Through this Hotspot analysis, Utilized excel data Regarding to Traffic data as csv folder to Arc GIS and Applied it to Hotspot Analysis tool and Assigned it as input. Then output displayed, Hotspot locations with values. As well as utilized IDW tool for Assigned, Input as Traffic data file and also z value as GiZscore in order to take spatial variation of hotspot locations through IDW Tool. This analysis pinpointed specific locations and times with severe congestion, validating the hypotheses and providing a clear understanding of congestion patterns.

This highlighted problematic areas and supported targeted traffic management strategies. By identifying traffic congestion hotspots, authorities can prioritize interventions and allocate resources effectively. The analysis will help improve traffic flow, enhance transportation experiences, and reduce the adverse impacts of congestion on the community. The goal is to use hotspot analysis to provide a foundation for informed decision-making and strategic traffic management in the Mirihana Police Division.

Figure 12: Hotspot map of MPD and Its Spatial Variation

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Excel Data From Traffic Police, Mirihana Police Traffic Sector and Questionior.

Traffic congestion is a major challenge in urban areas, affecting daily commutes and economic productivity. The Mirihana Police Division (MPD), a key area in Sri Lanka, faces significant traffic issues. To address this, aim to demarcate traffic congestion hotspots using hotspot analysis.

Hotspot analysis is a spatial technique used to identify areas with high levels of activity. For this study, we selected 20 locations within the MPD. The analysis reveals that Nawala Road depicts a not significant level of

congestion. However, other locations show congestion levels at or above the 90% confidence level, indicating severe traffic issues in those areas.

In hotspot analysis, the terms "cold spots" and "hotspots" refer to areas identified based on the density and distribution of a specific phenomenon or variable, often used in geographical and spatial analysis to highlight areas of varying intensity or activity.

Hotspots are areas where there is a significantly higher concentration or intensity of a particular variable compared to other areas. In the context of traffic congestion, for example, hotspots would be areas where traffic congestion is significantly worse than in other parts of the study area. These areas often require special attention for intervention and management.

Cold spots are areas where there is a significantly lower concentration or intensity of the particular variable compared to other areas. For traffic congestion analysis, cold spots would be areas where traffic flow is smooth and congestion is minimal.

Most of points in a hotspot analysis are displayed in red color, indicating hotspots, it generally means that the entire study area or dataset is experiencing a high intensity of the variable being analyzed.

- When a result is said to be significant at the 99% confidence level, it means that there is only a 1% probability that the observed pattern or result is due to random chance typically, in hotspot analysis, areas with 99% confidence might be colored in a darker shade of red to indicate very strong hotspots.
- When a result is significant at the 95% confidence level, it means that there is a 5% probability that the observed pattern or result is due to random chance. Areas with 95% confidence might be colored in a lighter shade of red compared to the 99% confidence areas.
- When a result is not significant, it means that the observed pattern or result could very likely be due to random chance. Typically, this implies a confidence level lower than 95%. Areas that are not significant might not be colored in red. They might be shown in neutral colors such as gray or

white to indicate the lack of significant hotspots.

Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) is a type of spatial interpolation used to estimate values at unsampled locations based on values at known locations. When applied to hotspot analysis outputs, it helps with Identifies specific intersections or road segments with significant traffic congestion. By applying IDW, create a continuous surface showing congestion levels across the entire road network. It helps in visualizing not just the specific congested points but also the areas in between, providing a complete picture of traffic flow and helping in planning traffic management strategies.

4.3 Identify additional routes to reach destinations by passing Traffic congestion using Road Network analysis.

Traffic congestion presents a substantial challenge in urban settings, impacting travel efficiency, economic productivity, and the overall quality of life. In the Mirihana Police Division, escalating congestion levels demand innovative traffic management strategies. One effective approach involves identifying alternative routes to bypass congested areas, thereby enhancing travel times and alleviating congestion. The third specific objective of this study aims to achieve this by employing road network analysis, using GIS tools like ArcGIS, to pinpoint these alternative routes.

Road network analysis is a crucial technique in understanding the movement of people and goods through a transportation network. It involves assessing the connectivity, flow, and accessibility within the network to optimize travel paths and improve overall efficiency. In urban traffic management, network analysis plays a pivotal role in identifying congestion points, understanding traffic patterns, and determining the most efficient routes for commuters.

ArcGIS, a leading software in geographic information systems (GIS), provides robust tools for conducting such network analysis. The Network Analyst extension in ArcGIS offers a comprehensive set of functions, including route optimization, service area analysis, closest facility analysis, and origin-destination cost matrix calculations. Through the application of these tools, urban planners and traffic management authorities can strategically optimize routes, reduce travel times, and manage traffic congestion more effectively within the Mirihana Police Division.

The hypothesis that congestion locations and the Road network significantly influence traffic congestion was tested and confirmed through this objective, underscoring the importance of alternative route

identification as a critical component in mitigating congestion in the division.

To identify additional routes to reach destinations by bypassing traffic congestion in the Mirihana Police Division, a systematic network analysis approach was employed using ArcGIS. The methodology involved several key steps,

- **Creating the Road Network -**

The first step involved creating a comprehensive road network dataset. This dataset included various road categories, such as main roads, secondary roads, and tertiary roads. Each road segment was attributed with additional information, including length, travel time, and speed limits, to accurately model the network's characteristics.

- **Defining Congested Areas-**

To identify areas of high traffic congestion, polygon barriers were created using data obtained from field surveys, questionnaires, and discussions with drivers and passengers. These polygon barriers were assigned the WGS UTM 44N coordinate system to ensure spatial accuracy.

- **Setting Up Network Analysis-**

Within the Network Analyst extension in ArcGIS, the "Closest Facility" option was chosen to perform the analysis. This involved loading the datasets into the analysis environment, where facilities were defined as destinations and incidents as passenger origins. The congested areas, represented by polygon barriers, were also loaded to reflect areas that should be avoided in route calculations.

- **Executing the Analysis-**

The analysis was executed by running the closest facility tool, which calculated the optimal routes for passengers to reach their destinations while avoiding congested areas. The results provided a set of alternative routes that bypassed high-traffic zones, thus improving travel efficiency.

The success of the network analysis heavily relied on accurate data collection. The polygon barriers representing congested areas were derived from field-gathered data, including questionnaires and discussions with passengers and drivers. These discussions provided insights into commonly congested areas and typical travel patterns. The destination and passenger point shape files were also created based on these discussions, ensuring that the analysis reflected real-world conditions and user experiences.

Here outputs depicts 5 alternatives regarding different locations (Incident and Destination). These locations selected through field data collection from questionier. These are given below,

1. Shortest route to reach location in Nawala Road.
2. Shortest routes to reach Rajagiriya from different locations.
3. Shortest routes to reach Thalawathugoda from different locations in Mirihana Police Division (MPD).
4. Shortest routes to reach University Of Sri Jayewardenapura to Nugegoda.
5. Shortest routes to reach Nugegoda flyover from Pita Kotte.

1. Shortest route to reach location in Nawala Road

Figure 13: Map of Shortest route to reach location in Nawala Road

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Digital Data From Hot Export Tool and Questionior.

According to the map presented, two passenger origins were considered, one from the Nugegoda Flyover on High Level Road and another from Pagoda. Both passengers need to reach a destination on Nawala Road. However, the intersection of Nawala Road, Pagoda Road, and Old Kesbewa Road is identified as a high-traffic congestion zone. Therefore, this intersection was designated as a polygon barrier in the network analysis. To determine the optimal alternative routes for these passengers, the destinations were loaded as facilities and the passenger origins as incidents within the ArcGIS Network Analyst extension. The congested intersection was incorporated as a polygon barrier to ensure that the calculated routes effectively bypass this congestion point.

- Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from Near to Nugegoda Flyover was,

Figure 14: Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from Near to Nugegoda Flyover

- Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from Pagoda was,

Figure 15: Suggested alternative route for Passenger who came from Pagoda

2. Shortest routes to reach Rajagiriya from different locations.

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Digital Data From Hot Export Tool and Questionior.

Figure 16: Map of Shortest routes to reach Rajagiriya from Different Locations

According to the map presented, Three passenger origins were considered, one from the Nugegoda Flyover on High Level Road , Kattiya Junction and Wijerama Junction. Passengers need to reach a Rajagiriya destination by using Kotte Road. However, the intersection of Jubilee post is identified as a high-traffic congestion zone. Therefore, this intersection was designated as a polygon barrier in the network analysis. To determine the optimal alternative routes for these passengers, the destinations were loaded as facilities and the passenger origins as incidents within the ArcGIS Network Analyst extension. The congested intersection was incorporated as a polygon barrier to ensure that the calculated routes effectively bypass this congestion point.

- Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from Near to Nugegoda Flyover was,

Figure 17: Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from Near to Nugegoda Fluover

- Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from Kattiya Junction was,

Figure 18: Suggested alternative for Passenger who came from Kattiya Junction

- Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from Wijerama Junction was,

Figure 19: Suggested alternative for Passenger who came from Wijerama Junction

3. Shortest routes to reach Thalawathugoda from different locations in Mirihana Police Division (MPD).

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Digital Data From Hot Export Tool and Questionior.

Figure 20: Map of Shortest route to reach from Thalawathugoda from Different Locations in MPD

One from the Nugegoda, Pita kotte and Madiwela Passengers need to reach a Thalawathugoda destination by using Thalawathugoda Road. However, the intersection of Madiwela Junction is identified as a high-traffic congestion zone. Therefore, this intersection was designated as a polygon barrier in the network analysis. To determine the optimal alternative routes for these passengers, the destinations were loaded as facilities and the passenger origins as incidents within the ArcGIS Network Analyst extension. The congested intersection was incorporated as a polygon barrier to ensure that the calculated routes effectively bypass this congestion point.

- Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from Nugegoda was,

Figure 21: Suggested alternative Passenger who came from Nugegoda

- Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from Pita Kotte was,

Figure 22: Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from Pita Kotte

- Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from Madiwela was,

Figure 23: Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from Madiwela

4. Shortest routes to reach Nugegoda Town from University of Sri Jayewardenapura.

Figure 24: Shortest routes to reach Nugegoda Town from University of Sri Jayewardenapura

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Digital Data From Hot Export Tool and Questionior.

According to the map presented, passenger origins were considered, one from the University of Sri Jayewardenapura. Passenger need to reach a Nugegoda Town destination by passing Wijerama Junction Due to Picket around Wijerama Junction. However, the intersection of Wijerama identified as a high-traffic congestion zone due to that. Therefore, this intersection was designated as a polygon barrier in the network analysis. To determine the optimal alternative routes for these passengers, the destinations were loaded as facilities and the passenger origins as incidents within the ArcGIS Network Analyst extension. The congested intersection was incorporated as a polygon barrier to ensure that the calculated routes effectively bypass this congestion point.

- Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from University of Sri Jayewardenapura was,

Figure 25: Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from University of Sri Jayewardenapura

5. Shortest routes to reach Nugegoda flyover from Pita Kotte.

Figure 26: Shortest routes to reach Nugegoda flyover from Pita Kotte

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Digital Data From Hot Export Tool and Questionior.

According to the map presented, two passenger origins were considered, both from the Pita Kotte. But, Different Roads. Both passengers need to reach a Nugegoda Flyover in High level road as destination. However, the intersection of Pita kotte Junction, was identified as a high-traffic congestion zone, due to Election campaigns organized by Political Parties Offices around there as Sirikotha, Labour. Therefore, this intersection was designated as a polygon barrier in the network analysis. To determine the optimal alternative routes for these passengers, the destinations were loaded as facilities and the passenger origins as incidents within the ArcGIS Network Analyst extension. The congested intersection was incorporated as a polygon barrier to ensure that the calculated routes effectively bypass this congestion point.

- Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from Kotte Road was,

Figure 27: Suggest alternatives for Passenger who came from Kotte Road

- Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from Thalawathugoda Road was,

Figure 28; Suggested alternatives for Passenger who came from Thalawathugoda

4.4 Analyze the factors affecting to the Traffic congestions in Mirihana Police Division.

Traffic congestion in urban areas is often a multifaceted issue, influenced by various factors such as land use patterns, economic activities, and infrastructural elements. In the Mirihana Police Division, understanding these factors is crucial for developing effective traffic management strategies. This analysis focuses on using Buffer analysis within GIS to examine the distances from the impact of key points of interest such as markets, schools, banks, offices, railway stations, and supermarkets on traffic congestion. And based on it, Utilized Reclassify and Weighted Overlay in order to identify Impact level of these factors for traffic congestion.

Buffer analysis, a GIS technique, involves creating zones around geographic features to analyze their spatial relationships with other data layers. By defining specified distances from points of interest, buffer zones help identify how these features influence their surrounding environment. This method is particularly valuable in urban planning, environmental management, and transportation studies, as it aids in identifying areas impacted by specific factors and supports informed decision-making.

In this study, buffer analysis was applied to understand how proximity to specific land uses and infrastructure contributes to traffic congestion in the Mirihana Police Division. By generating buffer zones around markets, schools, banks, offices, railway stations, and supermarkets, the analysis identified areas most affected by congestion and quantified the relationship between these points of interest and traffic density.

The Hypotheses that the proximity of slope, schools, supermarkets and fairs, railway stations, banks, and offices significantly contributes to traffic congestion were tested and proven through this specific objective. The

results confirmed that these factors indeed play a crucial role in the spatial distribution of congestion within the division, providing valuable insights for targeted interventions to alleviate traffic congestion in the Mirihana Police Division.

In urban traffic congestion studies, reclassifying map outputs is a crucial step in spatial analysis that often follows buffer analysis. This process involves transforming continuous data into discrete categories that can be easily analyzed and compared. By reclassifying various factors such as slope, proximity to schools, supermarkets and fairs, railway stations, banks, and offices after performing buffer analysis, supports for better understand how each of these variables contributes to traffic congestion within a specific area in this case, the Mirihana Police Division.

To comprehensively analyze the factors contributing to traffic congestion in the Mirihana Police Division, a series of spatial analyses were conducted using Geographic Information System (GIS) techniques. These analyses aimed to integrate various factors that influence traffic flow, providing a holistic understanding of congestion patterns and informing effective mitigation strategies.

The first step in the analysis involved generating a slope map from the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of the Mirihana Police Division. This analysis provided insights into the gradient of the terrain, which is a significant factor influencing traffic flow and congestion. Steeper slopes can lead to slower vehicle movement, thereby increasing congestion, especially in areas with high traffic volume.

Subsequently, Euclidean distance analyses were performed for several critical infrastructures within the region.

- Roads- Buffer of 1000 meters was established to assess the influence of proximity to major roads on traffic congestion.
- Schools- 1000 meter buffer was created to evaluate the impact of

educational institutions.

- Banks- 500 meter buffer was delineated to consider the accessibility of financial institutions.
- Offices- 500 meter buffer was established to account for the concentration of office spaces.
- Railway- 300 meter buffer was defined to analyze the effect of railway proximity.
- Supermarkets and Markets- 750 meter buffer was used to assess the impact of commercial areas.

Each of the Euclidean distance outputs, along with the slope map, was then reclassified into five equal interval categories. This standardization facilitated a comparative analysis of the different factors affecting traffic congestion, ensuring that each factor could be quantitatively assessed on a similar scale.

The Reclassification process begins with the original spatial data, such as Digital Elevation Models (DEM) for slope and buffer zones created around key points of interest like schools and commercial areas. Each of these buffer zones is then reclassified into categories that reflect different levels of impact on traffic congestion. For example, buffer zones around schools might be reclassified into categories such as "High impact", "Moderate impact", "Low impact" and "Very Low impact" based on their proximity to the points of interest.

This reclassification is essential for two primary reasons,

- Standardization- By converting various buffer and slope data layers into a common categorical format, it becomes possible to perform comparative analysis across different factors. This standardization ensures that diverse datasets, such as slope gradients and distances to banks, can be analyzed together in a consistent manner.

- **Weighted Overlay Analysis-** Reclassified layers are integral to the weighted overlay process, where each factor is assigned a weight based on its relative importance in contributing to traffic congestion. For instance, proximity to major roads might be assigned a higher weight compared to slope, reflecting its more significant role in influencing traffic patterns. By overlaying these weighted layers, a composite map is produced, highlighting areas with varying levels of congestion impact.

In this study, the reclassified outputs of slope, and buffer zones around schools, supermarkets and fairs, railway stations, Roads banks, and offices will be analyzed to determine their individual and collective impacts on traffic congestion within the Mirihana Police Division.

Impact of Slope –

Figure 29: Impact of Slope for Traffic Congestion

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Excel Data From Traffic Police and Mirihana Police Traffic

The map titled "Impact of Slope for Traffic Congestion in the Mirihana Police Division" illustrates how the topography, particularly slope, influences traffic congestion within the area. The map categorizes the impact of slope on congestion into four levels, Very Low Impact, Low Impact, Moderate Impact, High Impact, and Very High Impact.

Red zones on the map, indicating Very High Impact, represent areas where the steepness of the terrain significantly contributes to traffic congestion. These areas are likely characterized by steep slopes that hinder vehicle movement, especially during peak traffic hours or adverse weather conditions, there by exacerbating congestion. Light Blue and Blue zones, signifying Moderate impact to High, suggest that these areas are also affected by the slope, but to a lesser extent compared to the Red zones. These might include hilly regions where the gradient still challenges traffic flow, but other factors like road infrastructure or traffic management may mitigate the severity.

In contrast, Green zones depict Low impact areas where the slope has a minimal effect on traffic congestion. These areas are likely flatter and more conducive to smoother traffic flow, indicating that other factors, rather than slope, are more influential in these regions. The scattered black dots highlight specific traffic congestion hotspots within the division. These hotspots may coincide with areas of significant slope impact, where steep gradients contribute to the buildup of traffic.

Impact of Schools –

Figure 30: Impact of Schools for Traffic Congestion

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Excel Data From Traffic Police and Mirihana Police

The interpretation of the "Impact of Schools for Traffic Congestion in the Mirihana Police Division" map reveals the spatial relationship between schools and traffic congestion within the area. The map uses a color-coded gradient to indicate the varying levels of impact that schools have on traffic.

Areas highlighted in Red represent zones of Very High impact, where the presence of schools significantly contributes to traffic congestion. These zones are typically located directly around school premises, where vehicular and pedestrian traffic related to school activities are most concentrated, particularly during peak hours such as morning drop-off and afternoon pick-up times.

The Dark Blue and and Light Blue zones represent areas with High and Moderate impacts, respectively. These areas, though not immediately adjacent to schools, still experience considerable congestion due to their proximity. The transition from high to moderate impact is likely influenced by the dispersal of traffic as vehicles move away from the school zone.

Further away, areas shown in Green and Orange indicate Low to Very low impacts, where schools have a minimal influence on traffic congestion. These regions are distant enough from the schools that the volume of school-related traffic does not significantly affect overall congestion.

Finally, the areas without any color represent zones with no impact from schools on traffic congestion, suggesting that the distance from the schools is sufficient to prevent any notable influence.

Impact of Supermarkets –

Figure 31: Impact of Supermarkets for Traffic Congestion

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Excel Data From Traffic Police and Mirihana Police Traffic

Map Interpretation of Supermarket Impact on Traffic Congestion,

The map titled "Impact of Supermarkets for Traffic Congestion in the Mirihana Police Division" provides a detailed spatial representation of how proximity to supermarkets influences traffic congestion within the area. The varying color gradients on the map reflect different impact levels, ranging from very low to very high.

The Red zones on the map, which indicate areas of Very high impact, are concentrated around supermarket locations, suggesting that these commercial hubs significantly contribute to traffic congestion. These areas are likely characterized by high vehicle density due to frequent consumer visits, especially during peak hours. The high-impact zones align with the traffic congestion hotspots, denoted by black dots on the map, reinforcing the conclusion that supermarkets are a major contributing factor to congestion.

Light Blue and Green zones represent Moderate to Low impact areas, typically found farther away from supermarket locations. These areas experience less congestion, likely due to reduced commercial activity and less frequent consumer traffic. The Orange colored zones marking Very low impact areas are sparsely distributed and generally located in the peripheral regions of the division, where supermarket influence on traffic is minimal.

Impact of Railway Road –

Figure 32: Impact of Railway Road for Traffic Congestion

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Excel Data From Traffic Police and Mirihana Police Traffic

Map Interpretation for the Impact of Railway Roads on Traffic Congestion

The map illustrates the impact of Railway roads on traffic congestion within the Mirihana Police Division, using a color coded representation to classify different levels of impact. The color gradient ranges from Very high impact (Red) to Very low impact (Orange), effectively showcasing how proximity to the railway roads influences traffic congestion patterns across the region.

From the map, it is clear that areas closest to the Railway roads experience the highest impact on traffic congestion, as shown by the Red zones. These zones represent hotspots where congestion is most severe, likely due to increased traffic flow near railway stations (Nugegoda and Udahamulla) and crossings. Moving outward from the railway lines, the impact diminishes, as indicated by the shift from Red to Dark blue, Light blue, Green and Orange . This suggests that congestion levels decrease with distance from the railway roads, as traffic disperses and fewer vehicles are concentrated in these areas.

The presence of traffic congestion hotspots near railway roads highlights the role of rail infrastructure in shaping traffic patterns within urban areas. The close proximity of railway stations likely contributes to increased vehicle movement in these areas, leading to higher congestion levels. The gradation of impact levels moving outward emphasizes the buffer effect of distance, where areas further away from railway lines experience progressively less traffic congestion.

Impact of Roads –

Figure 33: Impact of Roads for Traffic Congestion

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Excel Data From Traffic Police and Mirihana

The map titled "Impact of Roads for Traffic Congestion in the Mirihana Police Division" highlights the influence of Road networks on traffic congestion within the division. The map is divided into impact zones ranging from "Very Low Impact" to "Very High Impact," based on the proximity of various areas to major roads.

Areas shaded in Red represent zones of Very High impact, indicating regions where traffic congestion is most severe due to the concentration and significance of road networks. These zones likely correspond to major intersections, arterial roads, or locations with high traffic volumes, particularly during peak hours. Blue zones denote areas of High to Moderate impact, where the road networks still contribute significantly to congestion, but the effects are somewhat less intense than in the Red zones. These regions might include secondary roads or areas that serve as major routes for commuting traffic.

Impact of Banks-

Figure 34: Impact of Banks for Traffic Congestion

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Excel Data From Traffic Police and Mirihana Police Traffic

The interpretation of the "Impact of Banks for Traffic Congestion in the Mirihana Police Division" map highlights the spatial influence of banks on traffic congestion within the area. The map, which utilizes a color-coded system to represent different impact levels, provides valuable insights into how the proximity to banks affects congestion patterns.

The map shows areas marked in Red as zones of Very high impact, indicating that these locations experience significant traffic congestion primarily due to their proximity to banks. The High volume of daily visitors to these financial institutions, combined with limited parking spaces and the frequent stopping of vehicles, contributes to traffic buildup in these areas.

Blue zones represent areas of High impact where congestion is also significant but slightly less intense compared to the red zones. These areas are still relatively close to banks, where the effects of increased traffic are noticeable but somewhat mitigated by factors like better road infrastructure or less dense commercial activity.

Light Blue zones, indicating Moderate impact, are further from banks and experience lower levels of congestion. Traffic in these areas is still influenced by the proximity to banks, but the congestion is less severe, suggesting that other factors like road capacity or alternative routes might help in dispersing the traffic.

Green and Orange colored areas denote zones of Low and Very low impact, respectively. These regions are located at a considerable distance from banks, where their presence has minimal influence on traffic congestion. Here, the impact of bank related traffic is negligible, allowing for smoother traffic flow.

Lastly, areas without any color indicate zones with no impact from banks on traffic congestion. These areas are sufficiently far from any banking institution, where traffic conditions are unaffected by the presence of banks.

Impact of Offices-

Figure 35: Impact of Offices for Traffic Congestion

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Excel Data From Traffic Police and Mirihana Police Traffic

Above map visually represents the influence of office locations on traffic congestion within the Mirihana Police Division. The map is divided into various zones, each depicting a different level of impact based on proximity to office clusters.

The areas shaded in Red represent regions of Very high impact, indicating that these zones experience significant traffic congestion due to the concentration of offices. These hotspots are likely the result of high traffic volumes during peak hours, as employees commute to and from work. Blue to Light Blue zones denote areas of High to Moderate impact, where the effect of office proximity on traffic congestion is present but less intense. These regions may still experience congestion, but to a lesser degree compared to the Red zones. Green and Orange areas, indicating Low to Very low impact, show regions with minimal office-related congestion. These areas are either farther from major office clusters or benefit from alternative routes that alleviate traffic buildup.

The core of the analysis involved a weighted overlay, integrating the various Reclassified layers,

- Roads- 20
- Slope- 10
- Supermarkets and Markets- 20
- Schools- 20
- Railway- 10
- Offices- 10
- Banks- 10

These weights reflect the relative importance of each factor in contributing to traffic congestion within the Mirihana Police Division.

The resulting Weighted Overlay output was classified into three categories indicating the level of impact on traffic congestion, Low impact, Moderate impact, and High impact. This classification provided a clear spatial representation of the areas most affected by traffic congestion and those with lower congestion levels.

Figure 36: Spatial Distribution of Affectinng Factors for Traffic Congestion

Source: Prepared by the Author based on Digutal Data From Hot Export Tool, NASA Earth Data and Questionior.

The map illustrates the spatial distribution of traffic congestion factors within the Mirihana Police Division, highlighting areas with varying levels of congestion impact. The Highly Impacted regions are marked in Red, indicating zones of severe traffic congestion, likely due to high population density, major road intersections, or commercial activity, surrounding these Green areas, representing Moderate congestion, acting as transitional zones where traffic intensity begins to lessen. The least impacted areas, shown in yellow, are primarily located in the periphery, where traffic flow is smoother due to lower road usage or simpler road networks. Additionally, the black dots mark specific congestion hotspots, indicating critical locations where traffic build-up is particularly severe, potentially due to bottleneck effects or key intersections.

CHAPTER FIVE

Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1 Conclusion

Traffic congestion is a pervasive challenge in urban areas worldwide, leading to significant delays, increased fuel consumption, and a diminished quality of life for residents. As cities continue to grow and urbanize, it becomes increasingly crucial to understand the factors contributing to congestion and to develop effective strategies to manage it. In the rapidly urbanizing Mirihana Police Division of Sri Lanka, traffic congestion has emerged as a significant concern, affecting daily commutes and economic productivity. This study undertook a comprehensive examination of traffic congestion within the Mirihana Police Division, employing an integrated approach that combined Spatial and Temporal analysis, Hotspot identification, Road network evaluation, and Factor analysis.

The Temporal analysis highlighted distinct peak congestion periods, underscoring the influence of various factors such as economic cycles, school schedules, and seasonal trends on traffic flow. The traffic density data for the years 2018, 2019, 2020, and 2022 provided a comprehensive view of traffic trends, illustrating the impact of various factors such as economic activities, urban development, and extraordinary events like the pandemic. The comparative analysis of these years reveals a consistent increase in traffic density year by year, except for 2021 due to the curfew. These insights are crucial for developing time-specific traffic management strategies aimed at alleviating congestion during peak periods.

Through Spatial analysis, the study effectively mapped out the most congested areas, providing a clear and actionable blueprint for targeted interventions. The ability to pinpoint these critical zones enables urban

planners and traffic management authorities to prioritize resource allocation and implement measures where they are most needed.

Furthermore, the Road network analysis, utilizing advanced GIS tools, identified alternative routes that could significantly redistribute traffic and reduce congestion. These alternative pathways are essential for improving travel efficiency and minimizing delays in response to growing traffic demands in the division.

Lastly, the Buffer analysis illuminated the multifaceted nature of traffic congestion, linking it to key factors such as urban development, road infrastructure, public transportation systems, and policy frameworks. The identification of low, moderate, and high-impact zones provides a nuanced understanding of how different factors contribute to congestion, enabling more informed decision-making. Overall, this study underscores the importance of an integrated spatial approach to understanding and mitigating traffic congestion. The insights gained not only address the specific challenges faced by the Mirihana Police Division but also offer a model for other urban areas grappling with similar issues. By leveraging advanced GIS techniques and a holistic analytical framework, this research contributes to the broader discourse on urban mobility and congestion management, paving the way for more sustainable and efficient urban environments.

5.2 Recommendation

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed to address traffic congestion in the Mirihana Police Division.

- **Implement Intelligent Traffic Management Systems-** Deploying advanced traffic management systems is crucial for real time monitoring and control of traffic flow within the Mirihana Police Division. This includes the implementation of adaptive traffic signal control systems that automatically adjust signal timings based on current traffic conditions, thereby reducing waiting times and congestion at intersections. Additionally, congestion alert systems should be established to provide early warnings to drivers about upcoming traffic bottlenecks. Real time traffic information dissemination through mobile apps and digital signboards will empower drivers with the knowledge to make informed decisions, potentially diverting them to less congested routes. This approach not only optimizes traffic flow but also minimizes the environmental impact by reducing idling times.
- **Utilization of Metro Count Classifier-** To effectively manage and mitigate traffic congestion, it is recommended to implement Metro Count Classifiers in the Mirihana Police Division. These advanced devices provide precise data on vehicle counts, types, speeds, and traffic patterns, which are crucial for informed decision-making in urban planning and traffic management. The data collected can be used to model traffic scenarios, predict congestion patterns, and design targeted interventions. By understanding the specific traffic dynamics in different areas, authorities can tailor solutions to address the unique challenges faced by each zone.

Figure 37: Metro Count Classifier

- Enhance Public Transportation- Improving public transportation infrastructure is essential for encouraging a shift from private vehicle use to more sustainable modes of transport. This can be achieved by expanding bus routes to cover underserved areas, increasing the frequency and reliability of public transport services, and integrating various modes of transport, such as buses, trains, and bicycles, to offer seamless connectivity. Additionally, ensuring last-mile connectivity is vital to make public transport a convenient option for all users. Enhancing public transportation not only reduces the number of vehicles on the road but also contributes to lower emissions and improved air quality in the region.
- Infrastructure Development and Upgradation- Upgrading and expanding road infrastructure is a necessary step to alleviate congestion in identified hotspots within the Mirihana Police Division. This includes constructing new roads where feasible, widening existing roads to accommodate more traffic, and improving intersections to facilitate smoother traffic flow. Creating dedicated lanes for public transport and bicycles can further reduce congestion by encouraging the use of these alternative modes of transport. Additionally, enhancing pedestrian infrastructure such as building sidewalks, pedestrian crossings, and

overpasses can reduce reliance on short car trips, thereby contributing to a more balanced and efficient transportation network.

- Promote and Publicize Alternative Routes- Actively promoting the use of alternative routes identified through road network analysis can significantly reduce congestion in high-traffic areas. This promotion can be achieved by installing clear directional signage, updating GPS maps to reflect these alternative routes, and providing real-time traffic updates to guide drivers towards less congested paths. Additionally, encouraging flexible work hours and telecommuting can help in distributing traffic more evenly throughout the day. The road network analysis conducted in this study identified several alternative routes that can improve travel efficiency, particularly during peak hours. Key alternative routes include,
 - ❖ Nawala Road- Passengers traveling from near Nugegoda Flyover should take Stanley Thilakerathne Mawatha, Railway Avenue, Purwarama Mawatha, 1st Lane, Wijewardenarama Road, and Nawala Road. For those coming from Pagoda, the recommended route is Pagoda Road, with a bypass road leading directly to Nawala.
 - ❖ Rajagiriya- For passengers near Nugegoda Flyover, the suggested route is Stanley Thilakerathne Mawatha, Pagoda Road, and Kotte Road. Those starting from Kattiya Junction should take Kattiya Junction, Rupasiri Mawatha, Cemetery Road, 1st Lane, Muttettuwa Road, Rajamaha Vihara Mawatha, E.W. Adikaram Mawatha, and finally, Kotte Road.
 - ❖ Thalawathugoda- For those traveling from Nugegoda, the route includes Stanley Thilakerathne Road, Edirigoda Road, Chapel Road, Alotiyawa Road, Galwala Road, Bodhiya Road,

Embuldeniya Road, Rev. Dharmarathne Road, Sigera Mawatha, and Thalawathugoda Road. Passengers from Pita Kotte should take Thalawathugoda Road, Bird Park Road, Rev. Rideevita Ariyawansa Road, Rev. Dharmarathana Road, Sigera Mawatha, and Thalawathugoda Road. From Madiwela, the route includes Embuldeniya Road, Koranelis Road, Thalawathugoda Road, Rev. Dharmarathana Road, Sigera Mawatha, and Thalawathugoda Road.

- ❖ Nugegoda Town from the University of Sri Jayewardenepura- Passengers are recommended to take Rubber Watta Road, Old Kesbewa Road, High Level Road, Old Kesbewa Road, and Nugegoda.
- ❖ Nugegoda Flyover from Pita Kotte- The route involves Kotte Road, Prof. Ediriweera Sarathchandra Road, 4th Lane, Ananda Balika Road, Pagoda Road, Stanley Thilakerathne Road, and High Level Junction.
- Policy Implementation and Regulation- Implementing targeted policies is essential for reducing traffic congestion in the Mirihana Police Division. This could include congestion pricing in highly congested areas to discourage unnecessary travel during peak hours, offering incentives for carpooling to reduce the number of vehicles on the road, and restricting the movement of heavy vehicles during peak hours to avoid exacerbating traffic conditions. Additionally, promoting the use of electric vehicles by providing charging infrastructure and offering tax incentives can contribute to reduced congestion and lower environmental impact.
- Community Engagement and Public Awareness- Conducting extensive public awareness campaigns is crucial for informing residents about congestion issues and promoting behavioral changes that can alleviate traffic pressure. Engaging with local communities to understand their specific needs and challenges can help in devising more effective and

accepted solutions. Initiatives like staggered work hours, telecommuting, and the use of public transportation should be actively encouraged to reduce traffic during peak periods. Community involvement can also foster a sense of ownership and responsibility among residents, leading to more cooperative efforts to mitigate congestion.

- **Ongoing Research, Monitoring, and Feedback Mechanisms-** Establishing a robust framework for continuous monitoring and research on traffic patterns is essential for the long-term success of traffic management strategies. Regular data collection and analysis will enable authorities to adjust strategies in real time and implement timely interventions. Setting up feedback mechanisms where the public can report congestion issues and suggest improvements can also ensure that traffic management measures remain effective and relevant. Continuous improvement based on ongoing research and public feedback is key to addressing the dynamic nature of urban traffic congestion.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

affairs, M. o. H. (2021). *Divisional Secretariat- Maharagama*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.maharagama.ds.gov.lk/index.php/en/statistical-information.html>[Accessed 13 sep 2023].

al., L. e. (2015). In: *Geographic Information Science and Systems*. s.l.:s.n., p. 480.[Accessed 13 September 2023].

Angel, S., Sheppard, S., Civco, D.L., Buckley, R., Chabaeva, A., Gitlin, L., Kraley, A., Parent,

J. and Perlin, M. (2005). *The dynamics of global urban expansion*.

Washington, DC: WorldBank, Transport and Urban Development Department.

Authority, R. D., n.d. National Highways. [Online]

Available at:http://www.rda.gov.lk/source/rda_roads.htm [Accessed 13 Sep 2023].

Batty, M. (2013). *The New Science of Cities*. MIT Press.

Beck, T., Demirgüç-Kunt, A., Levine, R., (2007). Finance, inequality and the poor.*Journal of Economic Growth*, 12(1), pp.27-49.

Bordass, B. and Leaman, A. (2005). Occupancy - Post-occupancy evaluation.

[Online] Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/285320244_Occupancy [Accessed 17Sep 2023].

Button, K. and Hensher, D. (2005). *Handbook of Transport Strategy, Policy, and Institutions*. Elsevier.

Cambridge Dictionary, n.d. 'Traffic congestion'. [Online] Available at:

<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/traffic-congestion>

[Accessed 31 May2024].

Charles, G. and Govert, S. (2017). Synopsis 15: Creation of bypass roads Safety Cube.[Online]Available at:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322790605_Synopsis_15_Creation_of_bypass_road_s_SafetyCube [Accessed 17 Sep 2023].

Chavhan, S. and Venkataram, P. (2020). Prediction based traffic management in a metropolitanarea. *Journal of Traffic and Transportation Engineering (English edition)*, 7(4), pp. 447-466.

Chilie, S. (2003). *Traffic Congestion: The problem and how to deal with it*. Chile: United Nations publication. [Online] Available at: <https://repositorio.cepal.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/d0851342-86b1-4aee-a262-0bedb95193cc/content> [Accessed 17 Sep 2023].

Crane, R., (2000). The influence of urban form on travel: An interpretive review. *Journal of Planning Literature*, 15(1), pp.3-23.

Dammulla, D. and Mudunkotuwa, N. (2021). 'Urban Traffic Congestion: Causes and Solutions', *Journal of Urban Transport*.

Dammulla, R. and Mudunkotuwa, R. (2022). Analysis on the Road Traffic Congestion inColombo Metropolitan Area. *CINEC Academic Journal*, 5(1).

Degryse, H., Ongena, S., (2005). Distance, lending relationships, and competition. *Journal of Finance*, 60(1), pp.231-266.

Development, M. o. M. & W. (2019). Urban development Authority. [Online] Available at: https://www.uda.gov.lk/attachments/devplan_detailed/Development%20Plans%202019-2030/Capitalcity_Plan/Volume%20I/English.pdf [Accessed 17 Sep 2023].

Downs, A. (2004). *Still Stuck in Traffic: Coping with Peak-Hour Traffic Congestion*. Brookings Institution Press.

Edirisinghe, S. (2014). *Travel Time Analysis during Colombo Peak Hours*. University of Moratuwa.

Edirisinghe, A. (2014). Slidatest. [Online] Available at: http://www.slida.lk/slidatest/application_resources/images/mpm_reso/policypaper/pp5.pdf [Accessed 17 Sep 2023].

Ewing, R., Cervero, R. (2010). Travel and the built environment: A meta-analysis. *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 76(3), pp.265-294.

Farag, S., Lyons, G. (2012). To use or not to use? An empirical study of pre-trip public transport information for business and leisure trips and comparison with car travel. *Transport Policy*, 20, pp.82-92.

Gao, S. and Chabini, I. (2006). 'Optimal routing policy problems in stochastic time-dependent networks', *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 40(2), pp. 93-122.

Giuliano, G. and Dablanc, L. (2013). *Approaches to Managing Urban Freight*. Springer.

Handy, S., Clifton, K. (2001). Local shopping as a strategy for reducing automobile travel. *Transportation*, 28(4), pp.317-346.

Highway.org, 2024. Home. [online] Available at: <https://www.highway.org/> [Accessed 14 July 2024].

Isarsoft (2023). 'Traffic Congestion Analysis'. [Online] Available at: <https://isarsoft.com/traffic-congestion-analysis/> [Accessed 31 May 2024].

- Isarsoft, n.d. Traffic-congestion. [Online] Available at: <https://www.isarsoft.com/knowledge-hub/traffic-congestion> [Accessed 17 Sep 2023].
- Kim, C., Park, Y.S. and Sang, S. (2008). Spatial and temporal analysis of urban traffic volume. In: ESRI International User Conference, San Diego, CA.
- Kumar, M., Kumar, K. and Das, P. (2021). Study on road traffic congestion: a review. *Recent Trends in Communication and Electronics*, pp. 230-240.
- Kumarage, A. (1997). 'Traffic Management Strategies in Sri Lanka', *Journal of Transport and Infrastructure*.
- Kumarage, A. (2020). 'Infrastructure Projects and Traffic Mitigation in Colombo', *Journal of Urban Development*.
- Kumarage, A. (1997). Traffic Management Strategy for Colombo. [Online] Available at: <https://kumarage.files.wordpress.com/2015/03/1997-p-01-te-traffic-management-strategy-for-colombo-annual-sessions-iesl.pdf> [Accessed 15 Sep 2023].
- Levinson, D. and Lomax, T. (1996). 'Developing a travel time congestion performance measure', *Transportation Research Record*, 1564, pp. 1-10.
- Levinson, D. (2008). 'The Rational Locator: Why Travel Times Have Remained Stable', *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 74(3), pp. 309-321.
- Lindsey, R. (2006). 'Do Economists Reach a Conclusion on Road Pricing? The Intellectual History of an Idea', *Econ Journal Watch*, 3(2), pp. 292-379.
- Litman, T. (2021). *The Costs of Urban Sprawl and How to Create More Efficient, Livable Communities*. Victoria Transport Policy Institute.

- Litman, T. (2021). Evaluating transportation equity: Guidance for incorporating distributional impacts in transportation planning. *International Journal of Sustainable Transportation*, 15(4), pp.255-273.
- McDonald, N. (2008). Critical factors for active transportation to school among low-income and minority students: Evidence from the 2001 National Household Travel Survey. *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 75(3), pp.331-342.
- Mirihana, D. P. O.-. (2018). Spatial and Temporal Traffic data - Mirihana Police division. Mirihana: Traffic Sector - Mirihana Police.
- Mirihana, D. P. O.-. (2019). Spatial and Temporal Traffic data - Mirihana Police division. Mirihana: Traffic Sector - Mirihana Police.
- Mirihana, D. P. O.-. (2020). Spatial and Temporal Traffic data - Mirihana Police division. Mirihana: Traffic Sector - Mirihana Police.
- Mirihana, D. P. O.-. (2021). Spatial and Temporal Traffic data - Mirihana Police division. Mirihana: Traffic Sector - Mirihana Police.
- Mirihana, D. P. O.-. (2022). Spatial and Temporal Traffic data - Mirihana Police division. Mirihana: Traffic Sector - Mirihana Police.
- Mudunkotuwa, R. and Dammulla, A. (2021). 'Analysis on the Road Traffic Congestion in Colombo Metropolitan Area', *CINEC Academic Journal*, 5(1), p. 8.
- Office, S. o. P. (2015). Statistics.gov. [Online] Available at: <http://www.statistics.gov.lk/statistical%20Hbook/2016/Colombo/Table2.9.pdf> [Accessed 17 Sep 2023].

Paul, A., Longley, M. and Floyd, G. (2015). In: *Geographic Science Information and Systems*.

Ravish, R. and Swamy, S.R. (2021). 'Intelligent traffic management: A review of challenges, solutions, and future perspectives', *Transport and Telecommunication Journal*, 22(2), pp. 163-182.

Rodrigue, J.P., Comtois, C. and Slack, B. (2016). *The Geography of Transport Systems*. 4th ed. Routledge.

Santiago, J. and Chile, G. (2003). 'Complexity in Traffic Congestion: The Need for Multidimensional Solutions', *International Journal of Transportation Science and Technology*, 2(1), pp. 14-21.

Sanguesa, J.A., Naranjo, F., Torres-Sanz, V., Fogue, M., Garrido, P. and Martinez, F.J. (2016). 'On the study of vehicle density in intelligent transportation systems', *Mobile Information Systems*.

Shefer, D. and Rietveld, P. (1997). 'Congestion and safety on highways: towards an analytical model', *Urban Studies*, 34(4), pp. 679-692.

Sureshkumar, M., Supraja, S. and Sowmya, R.B. (2017). 'GIS based route optimization for effective traffic management', *International Journal of Engineering Research and Management*.

Tsou, M.H. (2004). 'Integrating Web-based GIS and Real-time Traffic Data for Intelligent Transportation Systems', *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 70(3), pp. 275-291.

Van Zuylen, H. (1997). 'Quality management in road maintenance', *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, pp. 169-184.

Wallestein, M.M. and N., (2008). *Community-Based Participatory Research for Health: From Process to Outcomes*. p. 544.

Wang, C., Quddus, M. and Ison, S. (2013). 'A spatio-temporal analysis of the impact of congestion on traffic safety on major roads in the UK', *Transportmetrica A: Transport Science*,9(2), pp. 124-148.

Wang, Y., Zhang, C., Ji, P., Si, T. and Zhang, Z. (2021). 'Effect of pedestrian traffic light on traffic flow accompany with pedestrian crossing', *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and Its Applications*.

WHO (2018). *Global Status Report on Road Safety 2018*.

APPENDIX

The following questionnaire was designed to collect data essential for achieving the specific objectives of this study on traffic congestion in the Mirihana Police Division. The data gathered through this questionnaire contributed to three key areas of analysis,

- **Demarcating Traffic Congestion Hotspots-** Utilizing Hotspot analysis, this section aimed to pinpoint areas within the Mirihana Police Division experiencing high levels of traffic congestion. Respondents were asked about their experiences and observations regarding traffic delays, bottleneck locations, and peak congestion times.
- **Identifying Additional Routes-** This section focused on Road Network analysis to discover alternative routes that can help bypass congested areas. Questions targeted the respondents' knowledge and usage of various routes, their effectiveness in reducing travel time, and the challenges faced while navigating these routes.
- **Analyzing Factors Affecting Traffic Congestion-** Using Buffer Analysis, this section examined various factors influencing traffic congestion, such as vehicle density, the presence of pedestrian crossings, the availability of bypass roads, road quality, and commercial activity. Respondents provided insights into how these factors impact their daily commute and overall traffic conditions in the division.